

D1.2 User group needs report and technical use case definition

Dissemination level	Public (PU)
Work package	WP1
Task:	T1.4
Deliverable lead:	Rupprecht Consult GmbH
Version	V1.0
Submission date	19/08/2024
Due date	31/07/2024

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Control sheet

Version history			
Version	Date	Modified by	Summary of changes
0.1	07.03.2024	RC	Conversion of UC Template to D1.2
0.2	28.03.2024	RC, MAPTM, VIF, VICOMTECH, IKA	Revised and clean version with inputs to chapters 2,3, and 4.
0.3	21.06.2024	RC	First draft version with Chapters 1,2, and 3 (including Annexures) with complete subsections.
0.4	03.07.2024	RC, MAPTM, VIF, VICOMTECH, IKA	Revised version of D1.2 with added inputs on UC definition and conclusion.
1.0	22.07.2024	RC	First complete version sent for internal review

Peer review		
	Reviewer name	Date
Reviewer	Esther Novo	19/08/2024

**Funded by
the European Union**

Project funded by

Schweizerische Eidgenossenschaft
Confédération suisse
Confederazione Svizzera
Confederaziun svizra

Swiss Confederation

Federal Department of Economic Affairs,
Education and Research EAER
**State Secretariat for Education,
Research and Innovation SERI**

Disclaimer

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or CINEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

This work has also received funding from the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research, and Innovation (SERI).

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Connected and Cooperative Automated Mobility (CCAM) solutions have greatly benefited from the integration of AI-based components related to perception, situational awareness, and decision-making. However, to ensure widespread acceptance, it is essential to develop trustworthy AI. In this context, AITHENA aims to propose a human-centric methodology for creating reliable AI functions specifically for CCAM applications.

The research activities within the AITHENA project will focus on building Explainable AI (XAI) models through use case demonstrations. These demonstrations will emphasize perception, situation awareness, decision-making, and traffic management systems. By addressing these critical aspects, AITHENA aims to enhance the trustworthiness of AI solutions in the CCAM domain.

The impact of the developed solutions will extend to various stakeholders, including autonomous vehicle (AV) users, non-AV users (such as pedestrians and cyclists), CCAM solution developers, and decision-makers. Gathering requirements from these user groups—focusing on their mobility needs, expectations, and concerns related to CCAM implementation—is crucial. Additionally, AITHENA will address technical use cases based on their respective strategies, solutions, scenarios, and requirements, taking into account the identified user group needs and expectations.

This deliverable contributes to the objective of gathering user requirements by presenting the current status quo and providing insights into user perspectives on autonomous vehicles and artificial intelligence. Survey results play a key role in informing the AITHENA use cases, reflecting the diverse viewpoints of users.

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LIST OF ACRONYMS

ACRONYM	MEANING
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AV	Autonomous Vehicle
CCAM	Connected, Cooperative and Automated Mobility
CPU	Central Processing Unit
DL	Deep Learning
EU	European Union
FCD	Floating Car Data
FPR	False Positive Rate
FPS	Frames per second
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
HGV	Heavy Goods Vehicle
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LGV	Light Goods Vehicle
LOS	Level of Service
ML	Machine Learning
ODD	Operational Design Domain
OLR	Ordinal Logistic Regression
PI	Performance Indicators
RDF	Resource Description Framework
ROS	Robot Operating System
SA	Sensitivity Analysis
SFM	Social-Force Model
SAFEOD	Situational Awareness Feature Enhanced Object Detection
SLS	Semantic Labelling System
SUT	System Under Test
TM	Traffic Management

TMS	Traffic Management System
TTC	Time-To-Collision
UC	Use Case
VCD	Visualizing Categorical Data
ViT	Vision Transformers
VRU	Vulnerable Road User
V2X	Vehicle-to-Everything
WCET	worst-case execution time
WP	Work Package
XAI	Explainable Artificial Intelligence

1. INTRODUCTION

This chapter introduces the AITHENA project with activities related to WP1 i.e., ‘Methodology: AI Human-centric approach’ and linked tasks, focusing on the user needs and use case definition, the objectives of the deliverable, its intended audience, and the overall structure of the deliverable.

1.1. Project overview and relevance of user needs and use case definition

Innovative Artificial Intelligence (AI) has paved the way for the rise of Connected, Cooperative and Automated Mobility (CCAM) solutions. These AI systems can learn from vast quantities of data, enabling them to execute driving functions that surpass human performance in specific situations. The evolution of AI continues to foster the creation of hardware and software frameworks designed to handle and analyse expanding volumes of both real and synthetic data. This, in turn, facilitates the training of AI models that are progressively more precise.

AITHENA, a Horizon Europe project, puts forth a strategy for creating trustworthy AI functionalities for CCAM applications. The research activities are focused on building representative Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI) models for chosen CCAM layers (perception, situational awareness, decision-making, and mobility), which will be showcased in four distinct use cases (UCs). The project proposes the establishment of a common and harmonised methodology for the development and testing of AI-based CCAM solutions (perception, situational awareness, decision-making, and traffic management), with an emphasis on the pillars of trustworthy AI (accuracy, explainability, accountability, privacy, ethics). This is intended to cater to a variety of end users, including vehicle drivers, function developers, and certification/legal entities. AITHENA plans to make progress in three key areas of AI: DATA, AI MODEL development, and TESTING and Validation methodologies.

Figure 1: AITHENA Methodology with XAI and DATA along with four UC addressing CCAM solutions

Considering the four AITHENA use cases, i.e.

- UC1: Trustworthy perception systems for CCAM,
- UC2: AI extended situational awareness/understanding,
- UC3: Trustworthy and human understandable decision-making, and
- UC4: AI-based traffic management,

the second use case (in contrast to the other three use cases) is demonstrated through two parts i.e., collision prediction with hybrid AI data fusion models and robust prediction modules for robo-taxi in urban environment. UC1 is demonstrated through developing reliable pedestrian detection in urban environments. UC3 is demonstrated through the development of an explainable and robust decision-making (manoeuvre and trajectory) system, while UC4 will focus on demonstrating benchmark of AI models tested and utilised for traffic management and road authorities, involving data capture, labelling and conversion from real deployed systems.

To achieve the execution of the CCAM solutions developed in AITHENA, it is essential to first comprehend the user needs, expectations and concerns which will address the human perspectives as a basis for AI development in defining and re-evaluating different AITHENA use cases. This will lead towards the verification of the second milestone in the AITHENA project.

In addition, the results from the task associated with this deliverable i.e. T1.4 'Identification of user group needs, and definition of the use cases', will feed into different work packages within the project. For instance, in WP6 i.e. 'Impact: Exploitation, Dissemination and Standardisation', promotional campaigns aiming to educate the users about the use case developed in the project and promotion of XAI advantages in CCAM for the users will be executed through T6.3. These campaigns would be aligned with the inferences derived from the user group needs defined in WP1. Furthermore, the deployment of the use cases in the dedicated demonstrator platforms will enable the validation of the use case in WP5 against the requirements specified in the WP1 deliverable. With the principles of human-centric AI guiding the development of use cases in AITHENA through D1.1, D1.2 will further assist via definition of technical use cases and user group requirements.

1.2. Objectives surrounding human-centric approach

This deliverable is the second report of WP1 titled 'Methodology: AI Human-centric approach'. Following the definition of principles of human-centric AI in D1.1, this deliverable aims to:

- understand the needs, expectations, and concerns of different stakeholder groups on CCAM implementation, with a particular focus on those functionalities where AI solutions can be integrated.
- define the technical use cases in AITHENA addressing the strategy, solution, scenarios, and requirements with reflection upon the identified user group needs, expectations, and concerns.

1.3. Target audience

This deliverable will be disseminated publicly informing all interested stakeholders about identified user requirements and technical use case definition. These stakeholders include (but are not limited to) active mobility users interacting with AI-based CCAM solutions, users (or potential users) of self-driving vehicles, decision makers or planners, and developers of AI-based functionalities for CCAM applications and services.

D1.2 will guide AITHENA use cases based on the identified requirements, and foster deployment of the use cases in the dedicated demonstrator platforms.

1.4. Structure of the deliverable

This deliverable is structured into 5 chapters with corresponding description as follows:

- **Chapter 1** introduces the AITHENA project with WP1 activities linked with the development of the deliverable, defining its objectives, target audience and structure.
- **Chapter 2** focuses on the identification of gaps from the literature focusing on the understanding of user perspectives towards autonomous vehicles and artificial intelligence. This involves introduction to the methodological approach involving survey and workshops.
- **Chapter 3** addresses the methodological approach to collect perspectives from the public involving different stakeholder groups on the implementation of Cooperative, Connected and Automated Mobility (CCAM) solutions. The identified user groups and their needs, expectations, and concerns towards the self-driving vehicles (as defined in the chapter) will further detail the AITHENA use cases (defined in the next chapter).
- **Chapter 4** describes the technical use cases in AITHENA, addresses their corresponding strategy (including the rationale, objectives, approach, challenges, and risk), solution (including functional description, key technologies/AI-based models, scope and restrictions), scenarios, and requirements (including functional data requirements, operational requirements, legal requirements, and useability & human interaction requirements).
- **Chapter 5** concludes the understanding of the use cases reflecting upon the identification of the user group requirements and its definition.

2. CONCEPT AND METHODOLOGICAL APPROACH

This chapter focuses on the identification of gaps from the literature focusing on the understanding of user perspectives towards autonomous vehicles and artificial intelligence. This is followed by addressing a methodological approach which the deliverable follows post identification of key gaps from the literature. This is taken into consideration for the development of the public survey via workshops with the AITHENA partners (addressed in the chapter section), followed by the description of the four use cases via template with corresponding guiding questions.

2.1. Identified status quo from literature

A paradigm shift is taking place within the context of automation, with hybrid vehicles, autonomous and automated driving. The Society of Automotive Engineers (SAE 2021) classifies automation of vehicles into 6 levels with vehicles classified between SAE level 3 (i.e., conditional driving automation) and SAE level 5 (i.e., full driving automation) as Autonomous Vehicles (AVs). With the onset of new sensor technology and artificial intelligence (AI), AVs will relieve advanced driver assistance systems (Jarosch and Bengler 2018). This will introduce solutions and a new set of challenges to adapt, for the people using or interacting with it directly or indirectly. Focusing on the autonomous vehicles, future opportunities, barriers, user acceptance and public opinion needs to be addressed to reflect the status quo and ease of transition to AI via human-centric approach.

Parida et al. (2018) in their study reflect upon the advantages, opportunities, challenges, and user acceptance in relation to autonomous driving. Major challenges included ethical issues, cyber security, road infrastructure, and transition and regulatory needs. Within the aspects of user acceptance, based on numerical evidence from multiple reference studies, concerns amongst the users were identified (especially in developed countries) in reference to cybercrime, safety, legal and data issues. Some of the findings suggested how the public opinion was split with the positive and negative attitude towards autonomous driving. Reflecting upon the practical implications (Du et al. 2021), distrust towards AVs can be one of the biggest obstacles to the large-scale adoption of these vehicles. One of the reasons is less exposure to self-driving vehicles and the public relying on the mass media reports on these vehicles (which include negative reports). In addition, concerns over reliability of AVs in dangerous situations does not support the adoption of the technological advances (Liljamo et al. 2018) due to the negative attitude towards AVs.

Considering attitude towards self-driving vehicles, research shows variation across gender, age, and socio-economic factors. The study by Wang et al. (2020) reflects how, despite the wide variation in survey protocols and locations, a form of consensus was observed considering attitudes and demographic associations with AV perceptions. Considering different user profiles, men, early adopters of technology, tech-savvy groups who are aware of AVs and urban dwellers have a higher tendency to use or own an AV. The study also reflects upon the attitudinal factors influencing acceptance towards AVs (ranging from privately-owned vehicles to shared vehicles such as taxis). These attitudinal factors relate to technology acceptance, risk-taking, traffic regulation and driving enjoyment. While the results surrounding driving enjoyment shows no significant relationship with attitude towards AVs, the study from Asgari and Jin (2018) reflects that people who enjoy driving are less likely to adopt an AV. This shows contradictions in the attitudinal dimension of driving enjoyment. The results from Wang et al. (2020) also showcase how large fraction of population was not ready to use an AV without a driver and showed reluctance to share a ride in an AV vehicle (such as shared taxi

services). Many users also shared their concern towards taking back the control from the AV. While the study does not take into consideration the issues regarding privacy, security, or the impact of AV technology on the relative access to transportation, perspectives from other studies towards AV and technology (as mentioned in the table below) were observed.

Table 1: Perspective towards Autonomous Vehicles and technology through different studies

Type	Survey / Interview		Inference	Reference
	Number of respondents	Location	Perspective towards AV and technology	Author (Year)
Online survey	914 survey respondents	U.S.A.	Safety was a concern amongst females, those over 60, and suburban and rural residents. Females showed lower interest for automated vehicles. People with higher income were less likely concerned about security in comparison to respondents earning less than 50,000\$.	Lee and Hess (2022)
Online survey	8862 survey respondents	112 countries	39% of the response was categorised as positive attitude towards autonomous driving, while 23% of the response was categorised as negative response towards autonomous driving.	Bazilinskyy et al. (2015)
Online survey	482 survey respondents	U.S.A.	Considering the user profiles, males, young respondents, urban dwellers and people familiar with innovative technology showed high receptivity towards AVs.	Deb et al. (2017)
Participant interviews post driving simulation	68 participants	U.S.A.	Participants identified financial and trust concerns. Hacking and privacy were identified as integrity issues.	Buckley et al. (2018)
National survey	475 survey respondents	Ireland	Respondents were not interested in driving AVs with only 1/5 th expressing a high level of interest. Identified concerns surrounding data recording and privacy. Unsure about safety and security of AV's operation.	Rezaei and Caulfield (2020)
Survey	1533 survey respondents	U.S.A, U.K., and Australia	92% of the survey participants reflected high concern towards	Schoettle and Sivak (2014)

			safety of AV in poor weather and interaction between vehicles and pedestrians.	
Online survey	229 survey respondents	U.K., Spain, U.S.A. and Australia	Concerns about malfunctioning, purchase price, liability for incidents, interaction with non-AV, performance in unexpected situations, and cybersecurity. People with a university degree showed less concerns towards AV.	Thomas et al. (2020)
Survey	526 survey respondents	Seoul, Republic of Korea	Influence of innovation on public acceptance is mediated by public's perceived value of AVs. Public acceptance is partially mediated by their trust in AVs.	Yuen et al. (2020)
Expert Interview	18 experts	Australia	Limited exposure to AVs and complexity of safety and liability issues poses significant challenges to its adoption. Users more likely to have lower tolerance of error for AVs as compared to conventional vehicles.	Lim et al. (2023)

The findings mentioned above assist in defining an approach to further understand user needs, expectations, and concerns through the design and execution of the public online survey which will further detail the four uses cases in this deliverable. Overall, considering inferences from studies focusing on the public perspective towards autonomous vehicles and technology, major gaps are summarised as follows:

- There is a lack of comprehensive understanding of user acceptance of AVs involving AI and CCAM (i.e. Cooperative, Connected and Automated Mobility) technologies,
- There is a need to explore user interaction with automated vehicles and AI functionalities, especially regarding safety and privacy. Limited exposure to the technology poses a significant risk in its adoption.
- It is important to ensure that CCAM and AI technology is accessible and will benefit all members of the society, to have an equitable and sustainable transportation system,
- Identification of factors is required to build trust and transparency in an automated mobility environment involving AI.

Following the identified gaps, the survey for user needs assessment is designed and structured based on the workshops mentioned in the next section. For further details regarding background and context involving ethics, transparency, and privacy in CCAM applications, please refer to D1.1.

2.2. Survey approach

Based on the literature review identifying research gaps and exploring similar surveys for comparison during the later stages of user needs assessment and use case description, the survey design is executed (with results explained in chapter 3). The second phase involving survey design is a follow-up from the literature review, involving first workshop (as seen in the figure below). The objective of the first workshop is to involve AITHENA use case (defined in chapter 4) leaders and partners to define relevant questions for the survey. Post survey design and distribution, followed by data cleaning, survey analysis is carried forward. This involves identification of potential analyses to be executed along with the execution of second workshop. The objective of the second workshop is to identify areas of interest within the survey structure for analysis per AITHENA use case. Following this, the survey analysis is undertaken, and findings are documented into the deliverable.

Figure 2: Flowchart showing survey timeline involving 2 workshops

The final phase of the user needs assessment and use case description involves the dissemination of results. This is envisioned through different platforms with the publication of Deliverable 1.2 being a priority. Other platforms include potential publications through research papers in journals and website articles through newsletters.

2.2.1. Workshop 1: Design of the survey structure

As mentioned above, the purpose of the first workshop was to identify important questions to gather perspectives and understand the user needs, concerns, and expectations on CCAM implementation with focus on functionalities where AI solutions can be integrated.

The agenda for the first internal workshop was as follows:

1. Introduction to the Workshop (30 minutes)
2. Group work: brainstorming potential questions for topics (30 minutes)
3. Outcomes presentation (15 minutes)
4. Collective feedback session (20 minutes)
5. Feedback on questionnaire, delegation responsibilities (15 minutes)
6. Wrap up and next steps (10 minutes)

For the execution of the first workshop, the Miro platform was utilised. The Miro board included description of the survey focus by the four use cases as one of the input areas, followed by structuring of the questions within the sections of user profile, mobility needs, expectations, and concerns. The focus for the later sections is described as follows:

Mobility needs

Considering mobility needs, the focus was to identify and understand mobility needs of potential users, with a focus on the areas/interactions potentially affected by AI-based CCAM. This includes aspects such as road safety and personal security, people in rural areas where public transport is limited, users with mobility limitations (elderly, persons with disability, etc.) and travel time.

Expectations

Regarding expectations, the focus was to assess what each user group expects from CCAM services and the implementation of AI-based models in CCAM, about how users imagine such services will look, what their interaction with the technologies will be like; possibility to use time for other activities, and what type of impacts it could have on their life.

Concerns

Regarding concerns, the focus was to identify and understand the concerns and barriers that arise from CCAM implementation from the perspective of each user group, with a focus on the areas/interactions potentially affected by AI-based CCAM, such as data usage and privacy, ethical concerns, trust in the technologies, legal liability, mobility impacts (e.g., increased travel demand or prioritisation of motorised modes over pedestrian/cyclists), among others, and safety of self (or children) in an environment with CCAM in use.

As an outcome, the workshop led to feedback on the draft survey structure resulting in the identification and formulation of question and answers format, referencing similar questions to other surveys (learnings from EU projects such as 5GMOBIX, CONDUCTOR and DRIVE2theFuture, peer-reviewed research articles and other resources), allocating target groups for questions (users, non-users, etc.), rephrasing of certain questions for the better ease of understanding for the survey respondents, merging similar questions into matrices, identification of questions that were not relevant, including added perspectives and narrowing down certain aspects, re-allocating questions to different sections based on discussions and identification of next steps. Following the workshop, potential distribution platforms for the survey was discussed for the response collection and a tentative timeline was set to publish the first draft of the survey post revision.

Figure 3: Miro board utilised during the first workshop for designing the survey structure

Following a set of revisions based on the feedback from the project partners, the survey was designed and later distributed to response collection. Upon finalization of the survey design structure and data collection, a second workshop was held to prioritize survey analysis according to the use case needs. For in-depth information on the survey structure and identified questions from Workshop 1, please refer to Chapter 3 and Annexure I.

2.2.2. Workshop 2: Survey analysis according to the use case needs

Following the design of the survey structure, the second workshop was executed involving AITHENA use case partners to establish their interest for analysing the specific sections of the survey data. Concerning the survey data, the four use case partners had identified the type of data analysis that was of a priority to them. These included dependent and independent variables within the survey structure. Concerning the overall output, the two main type of data analysis that the partners reflected upon included descriptive statistics and logistic regression. For the logistic regression, the task included identification of relevant dependent variables and independent variables which would be analysed to explore any relation between them.

Figure 4: Miro board utilised during the second workshop reflecting UC needs. Right: UC responses corresponding to survey questions for independent variables.

Based on the workshop involving Miro board discussions, certain sets of questions were identified per use case to reflect upon the user requirements, expectations, and concerns. Considering the independent variables, these included (but not limited to):

- place of residence (i.e. either urban, suburban, or rural)
- possession of a driver's license or having access to a car (i.e. owning a car or car sharing)
- knowledge about self-driving cars or prior experience with riding a self-driving vehicle
- relationship with self-driving vehicles (i.e. developer of self-driving technologies and services, decision maker or planner, self-driving vehicle user, passenger in a vehicle with automated functions, active mobility user group such as a pedestrian or a cyclist)

Considering the dependent variables, some of the identified factors included (but not limited to):

- level of interest in using self-driving vehicle under different scenarios (e.g., owning a personal vehicle, using automated public transport, hiring on a pay-per-use basis, access to shared self-driving vehicles)
- level of importance to perform recreational or work activities while the vehicle is self-driving,
- frequency of travel in a self-driving vehicle for activities such as door-to-door daily commute (e.g., to school, work, or other), first/last mile of the commute (e.g., reaching a public transport stop), errands (e.g., groceries, shopping), leisure activities (e.g., sports, restaurants), vacation or journey to accompany others (e.g., children to school).

Based on the identified dependent and independent variables through the workshop, the analysis (including logistic regression analysis and correlation analysis) was undertaken. For more information on the survey results, please refer to Chapter 3 in this deliverable.

2.3. Use case template and guiding questions

Following the user survey design through workshops, the use cases within the AITHENA project were defined following a set of guiding questions. To address the use case description, a template with guiding questions was developed and shared with the UC leaders. The template aimed at capturing perspectives of UC involving its strategy, solution, requirements and testing and validation. While the strategy section addresses the rationale, objectives, approach and challenges and risks for the use cases, the solution section addresses the functional description, key technologies, scope, and scenarios for the use cases. The requirements section identifies the functional and data requirements, operation/performance requirements, legal requirements, and usability and human interaction requirements. Testing and validation section gives a brief introduction of planned testing, demonstration, and evaluation.

Table 2: UC template sections with corresponding guiding questions

Template section	Guiding Question
STRATEGY	
Rationale	What is the reason/need to have this UC?
Objectives	What are the major objectives the UC investigates?
Approach	Which approach does the UC take? Is it a virtual approach or physical approach?
Challenges and Risk	What barriers does the UC foresee from design to execution stage?
SOLUTION	
Functional description	How would the UC function? What steps or flow of functions are required for the UC?
Key technologies	What state-of-the-art knowledge and relevant projects, does the UC utilise/look into?
Scope and restrictions	Following the key technologies identified, which domain does the UC contribute to and to what extent? What are its limitations? This should identify key user groups (for e.g., drivers, passengers etc.), the modes of transport (e.g., car, public transport, etc.), the geographical area (e.g. urban streets including city centres, residential areas; highways etc.) the UC addresses.
Scenarios / use case story for CCAM applications	Following the key-technologies mentioned with corresponding scope and restrictions, how does the UC contribute to the CCAM application? Consider user needs and concerns through survey (T1.4).

REQUIREMENTS

Functional and data requirements	What AI models/algorithms are required to analyse specific objectives of the UC (traffic flow/identifying or managing incidents/adjust traffic signal etc.)? What kind of data is required (historical or real-time)?
Operational/performance requirements	What are the operational conditions (e.g. ODDs) that support the functioning of the UC? What are the major KPIs that monitor the performance of the UC?
Legal requirements	Are there any ethical clearances required for the UC development and demonstration? If yes, what do they relate to (e.g. informed consent, data anonymisation)?
Useability and human interaction requirement	What are the human interaction requirements for this use case? (e.g., are there are specific iHMI (internal human-machine interface) or eHMI (external human-machine interface) factors identified?)

The UC template was developed and integrated into this deliverable resulting in chapter 4 where the AITHENA UCs are described. Parallel to the finalisation of the use case description, the user survey results were analysed reflecting the user needs, concerns and expectations which influences and validates the proposed UC scenarios for CCAM applications. The inferences from the AITHENA user survey are shared in the next chapter.

3. USER GROUP NEEDS, EXPECTATIONS, AND CONCERNS ASSESSMENT

This chapter focuses on the methodological approach to collect perspectives from the public involving different stakeholder groups on the implementation of Cooperative, Connected and Automated Mobility (CCAM) solutions. This will particularly focus on the functionalities where AI solutions can be integrated, which directly contributes to the CCAM domain. The identified user groups and their needs, expectations, and concerns towards the self-driving vehicles (as defined in the section below) will further detail the AITHENA use cases (described in the next chapter).

3.1. Survey objective, scope and target group

3.1.1. Survey objective

The objective of the survey is to address and understand people's needs, expectations and concerns in relation to all types of road-based passenger vehicles (buses, taxis, shared vehicles, personal vehicles, etc.) which are fully automated and self-driving. For the survey, self-driving vehicles are defined as vehicles:

- in which the occupants of the vehicle do not participate in driving activities but must be prepared to take over control if requested by the vehicle for safety,
- which communicate on an ongoing basis with other vehicles on the road and with their surroundings (e.g. with traffic lights),
- that obey all traffic regulations (including speed limits).

The results of the survey will further provide guidance in understanding and addressing human perspectives as a basis for AI development in defining and re-evaluating different AITHENA use cases. This will assist in creating a comprehensive overview of perspectives of different groups, identifying key factors to build trust and confidence in AI solutions.

3.1.2. Survey scope and target group

With the opportunity to gather diverse perspectives for the survey, there were no geographical limitations for the online survey respondents (i.e., the survey was open to collect responses from everyone, irrespective of their country of residence). Based on the relationship of users to the self-driving vehicles at present or in the future, the target respondent profiles included (but were not limited to):

- active mobility users such as pedestrians and cyclists,
- users of a self-driving vehicle or a vehicle with automated functions,
- decision makers or planners involved in decisions as to whether self-driving vehicles will be allowed, and
- developers of self-driving vehicle technologies or services.

Specific perspectives of decision makers or planners, and developers were further identified in the survey results discussed in subsection 3.4.

3.2. Survey design and layout

3.2.1. Survey design

The survey design (followed by analysis) is executed following a literature review, preliminary description of the use cases from the ongoing developments in the project (for e.g., deliverable D5.1, which focuses on the testing and validation work of the four use cases), and a set of two workshops with the AITHENA partners.

Figure 5: Survey design involving literature study, UC description and workshops

The survey is designed based on the research gaps identified through the literature study involving user group needs, concerns, and expectations. Understanding of the status quo on perspective towards AVs and technology through different studies were captured through peer-reviewed journals, EU projects like 5GMOBIX (focusing on developing and evaluating automated vehicle functionalities using 5G core technological innovations), CONDUCTOR (focusing on fleet and traffic management systems for conducting future cooperative mobility) and DRIVE2theFuture (focusing on developing training, HMI concepts, incentives policies and cost efficient measures to assess connected, shared and automated use cases for users such as drivers, travellers, pilots, VRUs, fleet operators and other key stakeholders), and other resources involving international studies outside EU. Following the parallel activities defining the AITHENA UCs and workshops (as discussed in chapter 2) with the expert partners, the survey structure and typology of questions are set up.

3.2.1.1 Structure and question typology

The survey is structured through 4 sections namely user profile, identification of mobility needs, expectations, and concerns. A brief introduction of the four sections considering the allocated questions is given, as follows:

User profile

The first section within the survey focuses on the sociodemographic and socioeconomic indicators such as (but not limited to) gender, age, level of education, personal annual income, country, and place of residence. The section also focuses on the user's association with car, their knowledge, experience, and/or involvement with self-driving vehicles.

Identification of mobility needs

This section aims to understand the user group's mobility needs and preferences regarding self-driving vehicles. Questions in this section focus on situational factors such as preferred travel modes vs type of activity, importance of criteria for choosing a mode for daily trips, potential travel frequency in a self-driving vehicle, level of trust and interest towards self-driving vehicles.

Expectations

This section aims to understand the user group's expectations about self-driving vehicles, including how they imagine such services will work, how they would interact with such vehicles and technology, and what impact it would have on their daily life. This section also identifies the level of importance towards different types of information for an occupant/passenger of the self-driving vehicle and active mobility user groups i.e., pedestrians and cyclist on road.

Concerns

This section aims to understand the user group's concerns regarding self-driving vehicles considering a scenario where self-driving vehicles are widely available (e.g. personal car, shared mobility like buses or taxis). The section identifies potential factors discouraging user-groups using a self-driving vehicle and diverse perspectives involving interaction, liability, decision-making, data privacy and safety with the self-driving vehicles.

The questions are structured through identified independent and dependent variables in the survey (where majority of the questions are classified either closed-ended or ordinal questions). Based on the second workshop (as described in chapter 2), these variables were identified and later analysed using selected data analysis methodology (i.e. descriptive statistics and logistic regression).

3.2.1.1 Anonymisation and data protection

The survey incorporates principles of generalisation as one of the anonymisation techniques within the survey (also identified in the 0829/14/EN Article 29 Data Protection Working Party focusing on anonymisation). The survey does not collect any personal details from the respondents and all information is anonymised. The information on the project's [privacy policy](#) was also shared with the respondents at the beginning of the survey.

3.2.1.2 Translation

With the assistance of the AITHENA partners, the survey was made available in multiple languages including English (US), Brazilian Portuguese, Chinese (Simplified), Chinese (traditional), Dutch, English (UK), French, German, Italian, Japanese, Korean, Spanish, and Spanish (Latin America).

3.2.2. Survey layout

The overall layout of the survey follows a survey logic for different sections. This includes skip logic, display logic and termination logic. While the display logic used in the user profile and expectations sections, termination logic is used only once focusing on the user age group after the introduction section.

Figure 6: Survey logic flowchart with key sections

3.3. Survey dissemination

The survey links generated from the Qualtrics platform were shared through AITHENA partners and their social networks. This included partner's network of members, where FIA and IRU distributed the survey through FIA Region I members and networks, and IRU membership groups respectively.

3.4. Survey results

The survey had 445 overall responses out of which 326 were complete responses, and 340 responses had a completion rate of over 70%. Following the data cleaning and filtering out incomplete responses, the descriptive statistics and logistic regression results are shared through the survey sections as follows:

3.4.1. User profile

Based on the user profile of the survey respondents, there were approximately 50% more male than female. The respondent groups mainly represented the young and the middle-aged. Considering the level of education, majority had a university degree with more than 50% having a masters degree. Based on the socioeconomic aspects, majority had a middle or high range of personal annual income (i.e. >25000€) and represented urban population (i.e. >60%), followed by suburban and rural respectively. Based on the level of access to vehicles, majority (i.e. 80%) had a driving license and an access to car (i.e. privately owned or by car sharing).

Figure 7: User profile of the survey respondents

Considering the level of knowledge the respondents had about self-driving vehicles, 39% understood the concept well enough to explain it to others, while the majority (i.e. 54%) understood the concept or had some understanding about it. Regarding experience with self-driving, 42% had never ridden a self-driving vehicle, while 33% had some experience in a vehicle with automated features (with the rest having ridden a self-driving vehicle before). Based on the relationship (current or potential) with

AVs, the user profiles included AV users (47%), active mobility users (i.e. pedestrians or cyclists) sharing the street with self-driving vehicles (28%), developer of self-driving vehicle technology (18%) and decision-maker (8%) involved in decisions of self-driving vehicles' deployment and corresponding conditions.

3.4.2. Mobility needs

The survey respondents' travel behaviour based on their preferred mode of travel for the diverse activities was identified. These activities included door-to-door commute (e.g., school or work), first/last-mile activity (e.g., reaching a public transport station), journey to accompany others (e.g., accompanying children to school), errands (e.g., grocery shopping), leisure activities (e.g., sports, restaurants), and going on a holiday. Considering these activities, driving a car was a preferred for the three activities followed by walking. Scooters (and/or e-scooters) along with other modes were least prioritised for majority of the activities (as seen in the figure below).

Figure 8: Survey respondent's preferred travel mode vs activity

Considering survey respondent's place of residence (i.e. urban, rural, or suburban) the level of trust towards self-driving vehicles for travel in different spatial environments¹ (i.e. urban, suburban, inter-city (highways and non-highways), rural) was identified. The level of trust was low (or moderate) for the majority in the rural environment, while in contrast it was high for the inter-city highways. For the

¹ Based on the degree of urbanisation, urban areas (or cities) are densely populated areas, suburban areas are intermediate density-areas and rural areas are thinly populated areas. A city is a local administrative unit where at least 50% of the population lives in urban centres (having population density of 1500 inhabitants per sq.km.), suburban areas are areas with <50% of the population living in rural grid (i.e. not identified as urban centres) and urban centres, and rural areas are areas where >50% of its population lives in rural grid cells (Eurostat 2023).

urban environment, suburban environment, and inter-city (non-highways) the level of trust was mostly moderate or low (as seen in the figure below).

Figure 9: Level of trust towards self-driving vehicles in rural and intercity (highway) environments

Considering the level of importance towards different criteria to choose a mode of transport for daily trips, predictability, trip duration and personal safety were extremely important for many of the survey respondents. In contrast, the possibility to interact with others, individual services, or physical exercise was not an important criterion to choose a mode of travel. For in-depth results, please see Annexure II. Considering potential use of AVs in different scenarios, using automated public transport vehicles with fixed routes, stops and high frequency gathered high levels of interest from the survey respondents (as seen in the figure below).

Level of interest in using self-driving vehicle in different scenarios

Figure 10: Level of interest in using AVs corresponding to different scenarios

Following the use of automated public transport, using an automated shuttle service also gathered high interest from the respondents. This shows how using AVs not by driving but for commuting as a passenger was favoured in comparison to owning or having access to shared services of self-driving vehicles. This can be observed through the results where 37% of the respondents (the maximum for any scenario) were not at all interested in owning a personal AV, but this was seen as a contrast towards using automated public transport vehicles or shuttle services. Considering the potential frequency of using an AV for different activities, door-to-door commute was prioritised to be daily (34%), while first/last mile activities were mostly distributed on a yearly (22%), monthly (20%) and daily (17%) basis. For a journey to accompany others, using AVs was not an option considered for many respondents (i.e. approximately 50% responding 'never' or 'not applicable').

Potential frequency of travel in an AV for different activities

Figure 11: Potential frequency of travel in self-driving vehicles for different activities

For activities surrounding errands, while there was a weekly priority for 32% of the respondents, in contrast there was also an opinion towards not using AV for errands (i.e. 25%). For leisure activities, almost half of the respondents prioritised a weekly or a monthly frequency of using an AV (43%), while yearly frequency was favoured for activities surrounding a vacation (i.e. 45%).

3.4.3. Expectations

The user group’s expectations from self-driving vehicles are reflected in this section considering how the services work, the level of interaction and its impact on the daily life. The level of importance towards access to different kinds of information was reflected through the perspectives of an occupant of the self-driving vehicle, a passenger in a self-driving shuttle/bus, and a pedestrian/cyclist sharing the same road with AVs.

Figure 12: Information vs corresponding importance for the occupant of a self-driving vehicle

For the occupant of a self-driving vehicle, it was extremely important (70%) to know the situations where they were required to take control of the vehicle. In addition, there was a certain level of importance towards the type of information the vehicle’s sensors recognize and towards the understanding of the logic behind its decision-making. Similarly, for the passengers in a self-driving bus / shuttle, vehicle’s decision making and information recognition by the sensor had similar levels of importance. The presence of an onboard security supervisor (or backup driver) and acknowledgement of a remote security supervision were extremely important (as seen in the figure below) through the perspective of the passengers.

Level of importance towards information for the passenger in an AV (bus/shuttle)

Figure 13: Information vs corresponding importance for the passenger in a self-driving bus/shuttle

With pedestrians and cyclists sharing the same space as AVs, knowing decision-making process by the self-driving vehicles was of extreme importance (30%), followed by being informed when a human-driver is taking control of a self-driving vehicle and the presence of a self-driving vehicle itself (see Annex II).

On the importance of being able to work or do recreational activities in a self-driving vehicle, an Ordinal Logistic Regression (OLR) analysis was undertaken. This is done based on the workshop outcomes from the use case partners identifying key dependent and independent variables for OLR. The categories for the dependent variables are ordered/ranked, which assist in carrying forward the OLR. The single set of regression coefficients generated in OLR helps to estimate relationships between independent (e.g., activities one would like to do in a self-driving vehicle) and dependent variables (e.g., level of importance to do work or recreational activities). With the set of dependent and independent variables in the AITHENA survey, different relationships were identified. For instance, considering the importance of working or doing recreational activities in a self-driving vehicle, its relationship with the independent variables of activities one would like to do in a self-driving vehicle was identified. With the relationship being significant (i.e. <0.05), negative estimates towards reading, engaging in conversation (i.e. phone, with other passengers), and working on a computer or a tablet was observed (as seen in the table below).

Table 3: Case processing summary showing proportion of cases falling at each level of dependent variable i.e., importance to do work / recreational activities in an AV

Case Processing Summary		N	Marginal Percentage
How important is it for you to be able to do work or recreational activities in a self-driving vehicle?	Extremely important (1)	21	6.2%
	Very important (2)	79	23.2%
	Moderately important (3)	93	27.4%
	Slightly important (4)	72	21.2%
	Not at all important	75	22.1%
Which activities would you like to do in a self-driving vehicle? (choose all that apply) - Selected Choice Sleep	Sleep	140	41.2%
	NA	200	58.8%
Which activities would you like to do in a self-driving vehicle? (choose all that apply) - Selected Choice Read (documents, news, books)	Read (documents, news, books)	216	63.5%
	NA	124	36.5%
Which activities would you like to do in a self-driving vehicle? (choose all that apply) - Selected Choice Watch a video (TV, movie, series, etc.)	Watch a video (TV, movie, series, etc.)	159	46.8%
	NA	181	53.2%
Which activities would you like to do in a self-driving vehicle? (choose all that apply) - Selected Choice Use social media apps	Use social media apps	139	40.9%
	NA	201	59.1%
Which activities would you like to do in a self-driving vehicle? (choose all that apply) - Selected Choice Engage in conversation (phone, with other passengers)	Engage in conversation (phone, with other passengers)	199	58.5%
	NA	141	41.5%
Which activities would you like to do in a self-driving vehicle? (choose all that apply) - Selected Choice Work on a computer or tablet	Work on a computer or tablet	193	56.8%
	NA	147	43.2%
Which activities would you like to do in a self-driving vehicle? (choose all that apply) - Selected Choice Other	Other	12	3.5%
	NA	328	96.5%
Valid		340	100.0%
Total		340	

Table 4: Estimates showing level of significance and model fitting information.

		Parameter Estimates					95% Confidence Interval	
		Estimate	Std. Error	Wald	df	Sig.	Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Threshold	[Q4.6_ImpOtherActivREC = 1]	-6.634	.400	274.926	1	<.001	-7.418	-5.850
	[Q4.6_ImpOtherActivREC = 2]	-4.466	.327	186.097	1	<.001	-5.108	-3.824
	[Q4.6_ImpOtherActivREC = 3]	-2.758	.272	102.978	1	<.001	-3.291	-2.226
	[Q4.6_ImpOtherActivREC = 4]	-.785	.202	15.050	1	<.001	-1.181	-.388
Location	[Q4.7_1_ActivinAVSleep=1]	-.503	.242	4.308	1	.038	-.978	-.028
	[Q4.7_1_ActivinAVSleep=2]	0 ^a	.	.	0	.	.	.
	[Q4.7_2_ActivinAVRead=1]	-1.639	.313	27.393	1	<.001	-2.253	-1.025
	[Q4.7_2_ActivinAVRead=2]	0 ^a	.	.	0	.	.	.
	[Q4.7_3_ActivinAVWatch=1]	-.457	.255	3.193	1	.074	-.957	.044
	[Q4.7_3_ActivinAVWatch=2]	0 ^a	.	.	0	.	.	.
	[Q4.7_5_ActivinAVApps=1]	-.035	.246	.021	1	.885	-.517	.446
	[Q4.7_5_ActivinAVApps=2]	0 ^a	.	.	0	.	.	.
	[Q4.7_7_ActivinAVConvers=1]	-1.171	.271	18.648	1	<.001	-1.702	-.639
	[Q4.7_7_ActivinAVConvers=2]	0 ^a	.	.	0	.	.	.
	[Q4.7_8_ActivinAVWork=1]	-1.197	.283	17.905	1	<.001	-1.752	-.643
	[Q4.7_8_ActivinAVWork=2]	0 ^a	.	.	0	.	.	.
	[Q4.7_6_ActivinAVOther=1]	-.759	.555	1.871	1	.171	-1.847	.329
[Q4.7_6_ActivinAVOther=2]	0 ^a	.	.	0	.	.	.	

Link function: Logit.

a. This parameter is set to zero because it is redundant.

Model Fitting Information

Model	-2 Log Likelihood	Chi-Square	df	Sig.
Intercept Only	652.809			
Final	411.935	240.875	7	<.001

Link function: Logit.

The OLR above shows that there is a significant relation between the dependent and independent variables with model fitting information being significant (i.e., <0.05). In addition, the negative estimates for independent variables i.e., reading, engaging in a conversation (phone and other passengers) and working on a computer or tablet, with sig. < 0.001, shows higher chance of the category belonging to a lower category (e.g., 1 or 2) of the dependent variable. In other words, these

activities (i.e., reading, engaging in a conversation, and working on a computer / tablet) were very or extremely important as activities to do in a self-driving vehicle. Similarly other relationships between dependent and independent variables have been identified in the survey applying OLR analysis in ANNEX II. These relationships were considered through the workshop outcomes involving different AITHENA use case partners.

Figure 14: Needs towards self-driving system to be comfortable for doing activities corresponding to user’s level of understanding towards AV technology

In reference to the OLR analysis above, for different user groups (i.e., pedestrians / cyclists, AV users, decision makers, and developers) their corresponding needs for different activities were identified for a comfortable travel in a self-driving vehicle (see Annexure). The aspect of knowing the travel duration and route taken to reach the destination was favoured the most by these user groups. Similarly, respondents understanding the self-driving vehicle technology preferred similar aspects (as seen in the figure above) for a self-driving system to be comfortable.

Considering the mobility system of self-driving vehicles (including personal, shared, on-demand shuttles, and regular buses) that communicate with the surrounding infrastructure and coordinate actions (e.g., which route to take, speed) expectations from the survey respondents were assessed. Expectations towards better safety was reflected with low frequency of vehicle crashes (as seen in the figure below). Similarly, strong agreement was reflected in expecting better ease in switching to manual driving mode whenever the user of a personal vehicle desired to do so. In contrast, there was a degree of disagreement reflected towards accessing locations in a self-driving vehicle which was not previously accessible without a self-driving vehicle.

Figure 15: User expectations towards different impacts of an AV mobility system

Furthermore, expectations towards trips taking less time, less traffic congestion, the AV mobility system being more environmentally sustainable and fewer vehicles on the road were reflected through the survey results (see Annex II). In addition, considering expectations towards AVs being certified by official organizations or standards, majority believed the government and the overarching authority (e.g., the EU) to be the responsible body, followed by vehicle authorities (country/state), and independent standard organizations. In contrast, the respondents did not prioritize an organization representing automotive industry as a body to do the certification if required.

3.4.4. Concerns

This section reflects upon the survey respondent’s concerns regarding self-driving vehicles and different scenarios associated with it, along with the factors discouraging use of self-driving vehicles.

Majority of the user groups trusted to some extent that a self-driving vehicle would safely take them to their destinations and felt comfortable with AV’s ability to interact with human-driven vehicles. In contrast there was a degree of disagreement towards users being comfortable with allowing their school-aged children to travel alone in a self-driving vehicle. Similarly, there was a degree of concern towards self-driving vehicles being trustworthy to be safe and reliable in extreme conditions (e.g., rain, fog, snow, and darkness), regarding user’s privacy to be protected while using self-driving vehicle, and protection from cybersecurity breaches or data theft in a self-driving vehicle. There was a high degree of disagreement towards the users being comfortable about AVs making critical decisions, where harm to humans is unavoidable.

Figure 16: Concerns towards trusting a self-driving vehicle and comfort with the ability of AVs interacting with human-driven vehicles

Figure 17: Concerns towards privacy and reliability of AVs in extreme conditions

There was no strong agreement (or disagreement) on whether the occupants felt comfortable without control in an AV. Regarding level of comfort towards sharing the road with self-driving vehicles, pedestrians showed a degree of disagreement while AV users and developers showed a degree of agreement. There were less concerns regarding AV's behaviour towards people regardless of their appearance (i.e. clothing, race, gender etc.), liability for decisions made by AVs in which the respondents were the occupants and the ability to learn to operate a self-driving vehicle.

Factors discouraging riding a self-driving car

Figure 18: Factors discouraging use of AVs

Lastly, considering the major factors discouraging the use of self-driving vehicles were identified. The three most important factors included equipment or system failure, cyberattacks against computer systems and legal liability for occupants in case of a crash. In contrast, learning to use a self-driving vehicle was the least concern amongst the survey respondents.

4. USE CASE DESCRIPTION

4.1. Trustworthy perception systems for CCAM

4.1.1. Strategy

Rationale

The development of trusted AI systems for CCAM applications is important for deploying AI-driven products and fostering trust in them. AI-driven perception systems leverage the power of redundant sensors. Cameras, LiDAR, and radar, each with their own strengths and weaknesses, provide a wealth of complementary data about the environment around the ego vehicle. This data must be intelligently fused to create a richer, more comprehensive picture. However, sensor readings aren't perfect and can sometimes contradict each other. Furthermore, AI-driven products are very complex and are typically considered as black-boxes. This use case seeks to address these critical aspects to foster reliable and explainable pedestrian detection in urban environments for CCAM applications.

Objectives

This use case involves primary and secondary objectives. These are mentioned as follows:

- Primary objective: To facilitate the utilisation of a pedestrian detection system deployed in a demonstrator vehicle. This aims to enhance safety measures, especially in scenarios where pedestrian detection lies within the safety-critical path. For example, a pedestrian that is crossing the road and that might collide with the AV if no action is taken.
- Secondary objective: To showcase a multifaceted approach by integrating model-driven, data-driven, and sensor driven methodologies (further explained in the subsections below). This helps in ensuring reliability, explainability, and transparency of the pedestrian detection system and the associated AI-functionalities across the software, sensor, and AI stack.

Approach

This use case follows the AITHENA cycle, which is divided into steps involving physical and virtual approach:

First AITHENA cycle offline demonstrator:

The first demonstration is based on either the recorded data from the demonstrator vehicle, simulated data or based on the existing available public datasets on perception. This helps in fast prototyping, testing, and evaluating different approaches developed in the project.

Second AITHENA cycle online demonstrator:

The demonstration will be carried with one of the demonstrator vehicles on one of the proving grounds. The tested and evaluated XAI (i.e. Explainable Artificial Intelligence) methods from the first cycle are integrated into the software stack of the demonstrator vehicle and can be executed during the runtime of the perception system. In addition to the demonstrator vehicle, static components of this use case will be showcased to explain and document the integrated AI functionalities in the real-world demonstrator.

Figure 19: First AITHENA cycle components for the use case (UC1)

As mentioned in the objectives above, different strategies are researched and developed within the WP2 and WP3 framework. The overview for these strategies is as follows:

- Model-driven approaches:
 - Explainable layers: This involves implementation of transparent layers within the model architecture to enhance interpretability and comprehension of decisions. This aspect can be regarded as the main innovation for the first use case.
 - Visualisation XAI interface: This involves development of a user-friendly interface to visualise the explainable components, supporting a better understanding of the system's decision-making process.
 - Model cards: This involves creation and maintenance of model documentation to summarise crucial details across the machine learning (ML) lifecycle.
- Data-driven approaches:
 - Data cards: This involves developing and managing data cards to document essential information throughout the ML- lifecycle.
- Sensor-driven fusion approaches:
 - Reliable fusion of sensor modalities: This involves integration of multiple sensor modalities to ensure robust and reliable pedestrian detection. To address discrepancies in the data from diverse sources, safety mechanisms are incorporated.
 - Explainable multi-object tracking: This involves implementation of explainable methods for tracking multiple objects, enhancing system transparency in monitoring pedestrian movements.

The fusion of these approaches is instrumental to enable accurate pedestrian detection based on diverse sensor data and to ensure the interpretability of reliability of the system. This caters to the safety-critical applications within urban settings. The figure above shows the interaction between different components of UC1. Model cards, data cards, and ML lifecycle documentation are static components that describe and explain the AI functionalities used in the perception system. For the first AITHENA cycle, simulated and recorded data is used, which acts as input to the XAI perception system, generated by the demonstrator or by simulation. The AI black box functions are further enriched by XAI methods allowing users to better understand the inner workings and state of the AI. This information is made accessible to the user by XAI interface, which is a composition of multiple visualisations translating results of XAI methods into a human understandable format during the system's runtime.

Challenges and risk

Based on the approach for the first use case, following challenges and risks were identified:

- Explainability of complex models: While the use case proposes using saliency maps and visualisation techniques to understand the decision-making process of the AI model, explaining the intricate workings of a transformer model (particularly attention mechanism) effectively, remains complex.
- Data dependency and limitations: As the accuracy of the pedestrian detection system relies heavily on the quality and quantity of data used to train the model, potential bias or limitations in training data can lead to inaccurate real-world performance for the final demonstration of UC1.
- Limited scope of the demonstrator: As the initial phase focuses on a simulated environment or a recorded data (which might not fully translate the real-world complexities with dynamic elements), unexpected situations and domain shifts might occur for the final real-world UC1 demonstration.
- Integration challenges of the neural networks into the vehicle demonstrator: Integrating neural network responsible for the pedestrian detection successfully into the demonstrator vehicle's software stack presents a significant hurdle. This requires addressing computational limitations, real-time processing demands, and ensuring compatibility with existing software infrastructure of the vehicle.
- Lack of skilled workforce: Availability of qualified workforce with expertise in developing and integrating advanced AI methods is key to the use case's success. Shortage of personnel with necessary knowledge and experience in areas like neural network design, sensor fusion, XAI and ROS integration could act as barrier towards UC's progress and timeline.

4.1.2. Solution

Functional description

Based on the three approaches i.e., model-driven, data-driven, and sensor-driven fusion, the use case functions have been described as follows:

- Model-driven approaches:
 - Explainable layers: Within this approach, Vision Transformers (ViT) have been utilised where the transformer’s attention mechanism captures a global understanding of the scene and generates accurate detection and eliminates the need for handcrafted postprocessing or object fusion steps. A saliency map generation approach is proposed for a multi-camera transformer model, aiming to enhance the understanding of the model’s behaviour and provide valuable insights into which regions of input images are most influential in determining object detection predictions. The simple and effective method generates saliency maps during runtime of the model and outperforms expensive gradient-based methods. The effectiveness of the approach is validated through comprehensive perturbation tests.

Figure 20: Transformer-based XAI method applied to multi-view camera data

- Visualisation XAI interface: Within this approach, there are multiple set of functions and tools which are utilised leading to a user-friendly interface to visualise explainable components. These include model uncertainty visualisation, sensor usage depiction, attention maps, attention vector and ROS (Robot Operating System) RVIZ. Regarding model uncertainty visualisation, the interface should graphically represent the certainty associated with the model’s predictions. This is achieved via, for instance, display of confidence scores or highlighting areas of the image where the model is less confident in its interpretation. Considering sensor usage depiction, the interface should indicate which sensors (e.g., LiDAR, Camera) contributes significantly to a specific prediction (visualised by heatmaps or other graphical representations that emphasize reliance on a particular sensor data). In addition, attention maps would highlight the regions in an image that the model considers most critical for determining the outcome, in turn providing insights into the model’s

internal reasoning process. Following attention maps, attention vector would summarise the model's overall attention for the entire environment around the vehicle. The condensed representation offers an opportunity towards high-level understanding of the model's priorities while making a prediction. Lastly, the XAI interface can be implemented using ROS RVIZ, which is a popular visualisation tool commonly used in robotics applications. The tool provides the necessary infrastructure to integrate various data streams and render them in a user-friendly manner.

Figure 21: XAI perception system function overview

- Model cards: The model card template is developed for the AITHENA project within WP₃. It provides detailed information about the content that should be included in each section, with a user-friendly checklist to guide developers. Following the human-centric approach adopted in the AITHENA project, the checklist follows a user-friendly approach to request information from developers. It allows highlighting relevant elements to include and provides guidance on the amount and level of detail that should be included. This ensures that relevant information is presented clearly and comprehensively while being flexible to add more details about the model. This allows greater transparency and understanding of model and its capabilities. Within the UC₁ demonstrator, all models will have a comprehensive model card generated using the template.
- Data-driven approaches:
 - Data cards: Just like model cards provide insight into the AI models themselves, data cards offer crucial details about the data used to train those models. This transparency is essential for understanding potential biases and limitations in the system's performance. A data card serves as a comprehensive document outlining the characteristics of the data employed to train an AI model. It provides details across various aspects of the data lifecycle, including data source, data collection methodology, data characteristics, data limitations and potential biases. A data card template was developed within WP₂ and WP₃ of the Athena project. Within UC-1, complete data cards are provided for crucial datasets that are used to train detection models.

Figure 22: Data and model cards directly linked to the deployed AI functions

- Sensor-driven approaches: The system leverages data from various sensors like LiDAR, multiple (stereo-)cameras, and radar to create a comprehensive picture of the environment. Here, the focus lies on reliable sensor fusion: Integrating data from multiple sensors strengthens the system's ability to detect pedestrians accurately. Mechanisms are incorporated to address discrepancies arising from different sensor modalities, ensuring robust and reliable pedestrian detection. Furthermore, the system not only detects pedestrians but also tracks their movements over time which increases the robustness of the perception this. Additionally, methods are implemented to enhance transparency in this object tracking process.

Key technologies/AI-based models

Regarding the model-driven approaches, within the context of explainable layers (referring to XAI) Vision Transformers (ViTs) have made significant advances in the field of computer vision and found its application in autonomous driving (by achieving state-of-the-art results on a wide range of scene understanding tasks). The transformer's attention mechanism is utilised (which can capture global understanding of the scene and generates accurate detections), for the saliency map generation via multi-camera transformer model.

Different gradient-free and gradient-based computation and propagation rules are discussed as follows:

- The goal of each method is computing saliency map for each of the input camera images $S \in \mathbb{R}^{n_c \times H \times W}$ in the original camera image dimensions $H \times W$. In addition, n_q , n_t are the number of queries and the number of image tokens per camera respectively.
- The decoder-only architecture consists of only two types of interactions between the input tokens, i.e., self-attention interaction between the queries A_{SF} and the multi-modal cross-attention between image tokens and queries A_{CR} .

- In the cross-attention module, the queries are interacting with all tokens of all n_c camera images simultaneously. The interactions happen in each of the n_h heads of the multi-head attention for every layer of the n_l transformer decoder layers.
- During the inference of the model, the attention is aggregated which results in a multi-dimensional cross-attention $A_{CR} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_c \times n_l \times n_h \times n_q \times n_t}$ and self-attention $A_{SF} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_l \times n_h \times n_q \times n_q}$ tensor. As the model is conditioned in a set-to-set fashion, each query q will result in a classification vector y_q . Each element of this vector represents the sigmoidal class probability for all considered classes. If none of the class probabilities exceeds a certain threshold, the query will be regarded as background and won't be considered in the computation of the saliency maps.
- For the key explainability technology, only the *raw attention* of the cross-attention is considered. Following Chefer et al. (2021a) and a baseline is defined which takes the cross-attention from the last decoder layer

$$S = E_h(A_{CR}^{n_l})^+$$

where $A_{CR}^{n_l}$ is the last cross-attention map and E_h denotes an average across heads. Following Chefer et al. (2021a) and remove negative contributions before layer averaging. Different fusion approaches across *layers* of the transformer have not been explored by relevant literature [Chefer et al. (2021a) and Chefer et al. (2021b)]. Hence, we additionally propose a *mean-layer* and a *max-layer* aggregation strategy. The former one computes the mean across all layers and across all heads

$$S = E_l(E_h(A_{CR})^+)$$

whereas the latter one filters the maximum values across all layers and heads

$$S = \max_l(\max_h(A_{CR})).$$

Scope and restrictions

Considering the key technologies identified within the use case, target user groups include system users (i.e., the end-users), development engineers and researchers, and certification authorities and regulatory bodies. The end users relate to the group of people who are concerned with the overall safety and reliability of the system. They are interested in understanding how the integrated AI functionalities enhance safety, particularly in safety-critical scenarios. Clear visualisation and explanation of system decisions are crucial for gaining user trust. Following system users, the development engineers and researchers as a user group are interested in the technical aspects the AI models, including the inner working of the models, improving the model performance, robustness, or gather new training data to reduce biases. Lastly, the certification authorities as a target group are interested in the transparency and reliability of the pedestrian detection system. They need to be assured that the system complies with safety regulations and that the development process adheres to industry standards. Documentation such as model cards and data cards are vital for the certification process.

Regarding geographical area, the pedestrian detection system is primarily designed for operation in urban environments, including urban streets, city centres, and residential areas. These areas typically involve complex traffic scenarios with diverse pedestrian activity, making them the focus of the UC's development and testing.

Focusing on the modes of transport, the methods covered in this UC are primarily applicable to individual vehicles like cars and shuttles. Their applicability might be reduced for larger public transportation vehicles, where the passenger does not interact with the vehicle.

Scenarios/use case story for CCAM applications

1. Ego vehicle setting:

The use case scenario unfolds as the ego vehicle navigates through a complex urban environment, sharing the road with diverse entities such as other vehicles and pedestrians.

2. Challenges faced by the Perception System:

As it navigates, the perception system of the ego vehicle faces a variety of dynamic challenges caused by differing sensor inputs. These challenges include:

- View Obstruction: A visual barrier prevents clear sight of a pedestrian.
- Conflicting Sensor Data: Different sensors provide conflicting information.
- Sensor Malfunction: One or more sensors fail to function properly.
- Adverse Weather Effects: Poor weather conditions adversely affect the performance of certain sensors.

3. Conflict resolution by the Perception System:

- Effective conflict resolution (option a): Leveraging advanced XAI (Explainable Artificial Intelligence) methods, the perception system successfully resolves discrepancies from varied sensor data, making well-informed decisions regarding the detection and movement of pedestrians.
- User information and safe mode activation (option b): When conflicts remain unresolved, the system alerts the user by providing essential information. The user is then given choices such as switching to a safe mode or assuming manual control of the vehicle.

Figure 23: Schematic illustration of the UC-1 scenario. An urban scenario is considered where an obstacle blocks the view on a pedestrian.

4.1.3. Requirements

Functional & data requirements

Req. 1: Ability of the perception system to process multiple sensor streams from different modalities in real-time.

The perception system must run in the real-time in demonstrator vehicle where the verification means include the measurement of throughput in FPS which should be faster than the sample rate of the slowest sensor.

Req. 2: Ability of the perception system to detect pedestrians in the near field (i.e., <20m) of the ego vehicle with very high accuracy

This is required to have a reliable detection of pedestrians to avoid collisions, where the verification means include measurements with typical metrics for 3D object detection such as mAP, F1-score, accuracy, recall or TP and FP rates.

Req. 3: Ability of the perception system to provide user-friendly interface (i.e., XAI-Interface) to visually present conflict resolution decisions and information to the user during the system's runtime

The perception system's transparency and user understanding for its actions are critical for user trust and intervention when necessary. This is verified by conducting usability testing which ensures that XAI-interface effectively communicates conflict resolution information to the user.

Req. 4: Ability of the pedestrian detection system to demonstrate robustness in handling dynamic scenarios, including obstacles blocking the view, conflicting sensor information, sensor failures, and adverse weather conditions

As it is critical to ensure robustness for safe operation of ego vehicle in complex urban environments, the verification steps include conducting simulation and real-world tests validating system's performance in various challenging scenarios including those mentioned in the UC1 scenario.

Req. 5: Creation and maintenance of Model Cards, Data Cards, and ML Lifecycle documentation to enclose crucial details across the machine learning lifecycle.

For transparency, trustworthiness, and accountability of the pedestrian detection system the documentation is necessary. This is verified by regular updates and reviewing of the documentation throughout the machine learning lifecycle ensuring accuracy and completeness.

Operational / performance requirements

Req. 1: Measuring the accuracy of the pedestrian detection system by evaluating detecting rate, false positive rate, and false negative rate

This is required to verify the transparency, accuracy and robustness of the system by achieving a detection accuracy of at least 95%.

Req. 2: Evaluating system's performance in dynamic scenarios, including scenarios with sudden changes in pedestrian movements, unexpected interactions, and complex traffic dynamics

This is required to verify the transparency, accuracy and robustness of the system by successfully handling and adapting to the dynamic scenarios with at least 90% accuracy.

Req. 3: Assessing the effectiveness of the XAI-interface communicating system decisions and conflict resolutions to the user

This is required to verify the transparency of the system by successfully through usability testing of the XAI-interface where 60% of the users find the interface helpful.

Req. 4: Evaluating the transparency of the pedestrian detection model by implementing explainable layers and model cards

This is required to verify the transparency of the system by making sure that all deployed AI models have model and data cards. In addition, explainable layers should exist for key models.

Req. 5: Evaluating the latency of the perception system through inference tests on the used hardware (including CPU, GPU) and the inference speed is measured in FPS.

This is required to verify the accuracy and robustness of the system by making sure that the FPS of the sensor data processing algorithms is faster than the sample rate of the slowest perception sensor.

Legal requirements

Training data for DL driven detectors pedestrian contains often personal information. The detectors for UC₁ are trained mostly on openly available datasets. However, such models could be additionally finetuned with data explicitly collected for UC₁. In that case, this data will be processed by anonymization techniques like removing PII to protect user privacy. Furthermore, transparency is key: users should be informed and grant consent for data collection practices that comply with regional data privacy regulations like GDPR or CCPA.

Useability and human interaction requirements

This use case prioritizes the development of an explainable AI (XAI) interface for the pedestrian detection system. This XAI interface aims to visualize and explain the system's perception state, such as current certainty/uncertainty within the 3D scene around the ego vehicle. Furthermore, the perception system shares where it is currently laying its attention on, and which sensor technology is currently used for detecting surround objects. This concept paves the way for possible future HMI implementations that can effectively communicate with human users.

4.2. AI-extended situational awareness/understanding

4.2.1. Strategy

This section focuses on the rationale, objectives, approach, challenges, and risk linked with the second use case which is split in two parts.

Rationale

Use Case 2.1: Collision prediction with hybrid AI data fusion

AI models capable of collision prediction learn from images or raw sensor data to detect events and provide estimates like Time-To-Collision (TTC), cut-in probabilities, and other collision-risk indicators. These predictions offer a glimpse into potential near-future road situations.

Evaluating these AI models in real-world scenarios presents multiple challenges:

- **Data Collection:** Organizing a recording campaign using instrumented vehicles equipped with cameras, LIDAR, and other sensors is crucial. These campaigns aim to capture natural driving scenarios and specific situations relevant for testing the AI's functionality.
- **Data Annotation:** It's essential to annotate the recorded data to create a ground truth— an authenticated description of the recorded events. This ground truth helps compare the AI's output against the correct results and generate Performance Indicators (PIs).
- **Data Relevance:** The data used to compute PIs must be representative of the scenarios of interest. Real-world data often includes rare or edge-case scenarios (i.e. infrequent situations of interest). Filtering out irrelevant content is critical for obtaining meaningful PIs, reducing unnecessary testing, and conserving computational resources.
- **Labelling Challenges:** Semi-automating the labelling of perception-level ground truth can be done using existing AI models to perform initial labelling tasks, leaving human operators to

validate these results. However, identifying edge cases is complex for both automated systems, which may lack semantic understanding, and human operators, who may not have enough data to recognize these scenarios.

Test engineers tasked with evaluating the AI model (System Under Test, SUT) may struggle to sift through raw footage from recording campaigns to find scenes that yield relevant PIs. Supervisors or other stakeholders might require these engineers to explain how they selected the edge cases for clarity and transparency.

Accurate collision-related information necessitates precise spatio-temporal labels for road participants, such as pedestrians and vehicles. These can be represented using geometries like cuboids or polylines and other attributes to specify the object class (e.g., "pedestrian," "car"). The dynamic nature of road scenes is captured through temporal labelling of trajectories and specific actions occurring during designated time frames. The ASAM OpenLabel 1.0.0 standard is the first international standard defining how to represent this level of detailed perception labels.

Identifying edge cases in real-world data is inherently challenging due to the nuanced and semantic nature of such scenarios, like near-misses or cut-ins, which are often tough to label accurately by both humans and machines. A proposed Semantic Labelling System (SLS) uses logical inference based on user-defined rules applied to perception-level annotations to identify edge cases. These rules include expert knowledge defining actions of interest, making them understandable and interpretable (i.e. what the scene contains and the how edge-cases were found). This system facilitates, for instance, test engineers in filtering recordings and provides supervisors or clients clear insights into which scenes were chosen and the rationale behind these choices, enhancing transparency and understanding across different user groups.

Use case 2.2: Robust prediction modules for robo-taxis in urban environment

For robust and timely decision-making during navigation in urban environments, the robo-taxi must not only understand the current state but also anticipate the future states of its environment. While the current state would be sufficient for short-term decisions (e.g., braking to avoid collisions), predictions of long-term environmental changes are essential for comprehensive route planning. These long-term predictions primarily pertain to the evolution of motion among observed traffic participants. However, the time horizon width of future motion predictions isn't the sole determinant of the module's applicability. The decision-making module could leverage the model's added capacity to address uncertainty, particularly in scenarios with multiple plausible predictions. In conjunction, the prediction time horizon and uncertainty measures can lead to more reliable planning. These factors also show similarities between the situational awareness of a robo-taxi and that of a human driver. Human decision-making relies on abstracting the most probable intentions of surrounding participants, characterized by both long-term foresight and uncertainty. Guided by these factors, the developed motion prediction module can not only emulate the situational awareness of a human driver but also enhance it through vast data utilization and faster processing power.

Generating motion predictions faces multiple challenges due to the complexities present in urban environments. The existence of numerous interactions among different classes of traffic participants and road infrastructure elements must be considered by the prediction module. These interactions are rooted in spatio-temporal information about scene elements but may also include information on traffic regulations (e.g., right-of-way rules) or social effects (e.g., pedestrians moving in groups). It is assumed that a perception module capable of identifying crucial scenario knowledge precedes the prediction module. The minimum requirement set for the perception module is to provide traffic participants' state information (e.g., position or velocity), but the prediction module could take advantage of additional information such as traffic or vehicle signalization (e.g., traffic lights or turning indicators).

In conclusion, the prediction module supporting the robo-taxi's navigation has to meet the criteria of long-term foresight and prediction uncertainty. Framing the prediction problem within the urban environment context gives rise to more challenges including requirements of invariance to different classes of traffic participants and elements of urban infrastructure. However, further exploration of scenario information reveals opportunities for their direct incorporation into the model's design, enhancing its explainability and generalizability. Adopting such approaches allowed the addressing of different aspects of trustworthiness, namely, accuracy, robustness, and transparency, within the framework of UC2.2.

Objectives

Use case 2.1: Collision prediction with hybrid AI data fusion

The main objective of UC 2.1 is to produce a SLS, using graphical database technologies and a set of rules that detect edge cases and create rich explanations of the scene. Other secondary objectives include:

- Defining a data model for perception-level ground truth in a semantic graph, to enable execution of rules, based on ASAM OpenLabel 1.0.0.
- Demonstrating the utilisation of the SLS on a large dataset to discover edge cases where SUT performance can be evaluated.

Use case 2.2: Robust prediction modules for robo-taxis in urban environment

The goal of UC2.2 is to develop a trustworthy prediction module providing a robo-taxi with precise information on the motion of observed traffic participants. In an urban environment, such a prediction module is crucial for ensuring the safe, efficient, and comfortable operation of the robo-taxi by providing comprehensive input to the decision-making and planning module. Following this, the main objectives of UC2.2 include:

- Design of the module capable of long-term motion predictions (>3s) and uncertainty considerations.
- Inclusion of heterogeneous scenario information sources such as traffic participants' states and road infrastructure through data fusion.

- Integration of explainable approaches into the prediction module design and development enhancing the transparency and generalizability of the module.
- Demonstration of the prediction module in urban scenarios, primarily focusing on motion prediction of vulnerable road users (VRUs) interacting with a robo-taxi at intersection crossings.

Approach

Use case 2.1: Collision prediction with hybrid AI data fusion

The use case involves an approach involving several steps:

1. Firstly, it involves selecting a dataset of road scenes, with recorded images, LIDAR or other sensorial data, which is already labelled at perception-level, i.e., it contains sufficiently rich object-level data, such as the presence, position and class of objects around the ego-vehicle.
2. Following this, production of a semantic data model is devised to semantically model relationships between objects, using ASAM OpenLabel 1.0.0 as labelling format due to its inherent capabilities to model semantic relationships.
3. Convert the object-level annotations of the selected dataset into the semantically enriched data model.
4. Define edge-cases of interest (Note: it is essential to make sure the dataset contains some).
5. Develop the SLS and load the semantically enriched data into the SLS.
6. Prepare semantic queries addressing the edge-cases.
7. Run the semantic queries against the SLS and verify the results are the expected edge-cases.

The main feature (innovation) is the creation of a SLS that can produce semantically rich detections, as explanations of the scenes. The SLS can run expert rules, user-defined, easy to read by humans, to increase the interpretability of the searching process. This use case provides a general approach to label semantically any perception-level dataset. The SLS could be used to produce semantic explanations in the form of other actions or manoeuvre of road scenes that might be relevant for other use cases.

Use case 2.2: Robust prediction modules for robo-taxis in urban environment

To achieve the objectives outlined for UC2.2, the developed solution aims to find the balance in the performance-explainability trade-off. We propose an integration of two distinct approaches, each representing a different facet of the trade-off. The model-based approach, characterized by its inherent explainability, contrasts the data-based approach, known for its superior performance that comes at the cost of explainability. To leverage the benefits of both approaches, their fusion will be executed at a higher level, wherein the outputs of the data-based component will serve as the input to the model-based component. The integration will be performed within the framework of a Social-Force Model (SFM) capable of modelling not only the environmental forces (e.g., obstacles, sidewalk, or lane boundaries) but also social interactions (e.g., pedestrians moving in groups) influencing

detected traffic participants. Within the SFM framework, the data- and model-based approaches are represented as two distinct components: the force calculation and the motion model, respectively. However, outside the SFM, the expected input is a semantically enriched encoding of the observed scenario information (passed to the model-based component), while the output is the trajectory predictions of the tracked traffic participants.

The approach will be based on the following features:

- Generation of the intermediate input that encodes semantically enriched scenario information received from the perception system.
- Social-force model encompassing both a data- and model-based approach.
- Visualization of the predicted trajectories belonging to the detected traffic participants.

The success of the proposed SFM-based solution will be evaluated through two types of indicators, i.e., accuracy and feasibility. These indicators can be directly traced to the trade-off between the model's performance and its explainability. The goal is to generate trajectory predictions that not only closely follow the actual trajectories of the observed traffic participants but also adhere to the constraints imposed by the environmental factors and the dynamics inherent to the considered traffic participant.

The development of the proposed solution is undertaken as part of the WP3, specifically under the Task T3.4. With the completion of each development cycle, the model will be evaluated against the testing and validation methodology outlined in the T5.1 task. A parallel can be drawn between the situational awareness established as part of the UC2.2 and the UC3. While UC2 focuses primarily on the extension of situational awareness, UC2 demonstrates how situational awareness becomes an integral part of the decision-making process. At a broader level, UC1, UC2, and UC3 represent components of an AD pipeline, addressing distinct phases from perception, and prediction, to decision-making. Although interconnections exist within the pipeline, it should be acknowledged that component development will still be conducted independently.

Challenges and risk

Use case 2.1: Collision prediction with hybrid AI data fusion

Based on the objectives and approach for the UC2.1, following set of challenges and risks were identified:

- Challenges:
 - Creating the SLS as an ontology that represents the data model, a graphical database, and a rule-based query language aligned with ASAM OpenLabel 1.0.0.
 - Finding a dataset that contains edge-cases.
- Risks
 - Rules created using the SLS might not be sufficiently friendly for any type of user. In some cases, the rule can be difficult to read, despite it its written in a semantic language.
 - Expert rules are not easy to define and edge cases cannot be found easily, or too many false positives are generated.

Use case 2.2: Robust prediction modules for robo-taxis in urban environment

During the design and development of a motion prediction module, it is possible to recognize challenges and risks that are external and internal to the module. The difference lies in answering the question: Can the risk be addressed in the design and development stage of the model? While the choice of training dataset is the responsibility of the module developer, the performance of the module will still depend on the availability (external risk) of the dataset satisfying specific requirements. Similarly, it would be the responsibility of the developer to decide how should the obtained dataset be used within the module (internal risk) to achieve the desired performance. However, these choices will be made during the design and development stage. Recognizing this distinction, following challenges and risks are listed:

- External:
 - Compiling a representative dataset containing complex and dynamic scenarios inherent to the urban environment. The datasets should contain scenarios in which interactions between different scenario elements can be observed simultaneously (e.g. pedestrians interacting with other traffic participants, namely, vehicles while crossing at an intersection).
 - Availability of the required information sources, especially of the real-world scenarios in comparison to virtual-world scenarios. Availability of the scenario information might be limited if the datasets are generated from real-world recordings as opposed to those generated in a simulated environment.
 - Reduced robustness of the module against cases of perception module faults (e.g., noncontinuous stream of scenario information). At the design stage, requirements of the preceding perception module have been defined, but their enforcement might be limiting the availability of the real-world scenario data.

- Internal:
 - Choice of pertinent prior scenario knowledge and its integration into the prediction module. The module's generalizability to the unforeseen scenarios depends on the scenario knowledge introduced to the module.
 - Optimization of the trade-off between explainability and accuracy of the motion predictions. Reviewed state-of-the-art mark the superiority of the data-driven methods in regard to the accuracy metrics. However, these methods are of a black-box nature scoring low on explainability in comparison to the physics-based methods.
 - Granularity and fusion of scenario information. The performance of the prediction module will depend on the identification of distinct scenario elements that influence the motion of observed traffic participants. The choice of elements that describe the scenario and the approach to their interaction modelling will be crucial to the module design. Note that this challenge is related to the external challenge of the scenario information availability.

4.2.2. Solution

Functional description

Use case 2.1: Collision prediction with hybrid AI data fusion

This section overviews the architecture and functional description of the proposed development. Figure 24 represents the major blocks of the proposed approach.

Figure 24: Block diagram: Scenario extraction using semantic labels

The rationale starts from the need to identify high-level scenarios from datasets captured with instrumented vehicles in driving scenes. These scenes might be real or synthetic, as long as they contain data recordings in the form of data packages with sensor data (camera, LIDAR, CAN, etc). These data serve as the basis on which build the semantic processing pipeline proposed in this use case.

Therefore, the starting point is a set of datasets, which are processed to contain object-level representations of the reality. Typical objects include things, i.e., uncountable and countable entities that play roles in driving scenes, like pavement, lane markings, traffic signs, vehicles, bicycles, pedestrians, etc.

These object level labels shall then go through the "Data preparation" stage, to be transformed or re-shaped to follow the ASAM OpenLabel 1.0 standard, as described in previous sections. This conversion can be done with Python scripting using the open-source library VCD (<https://pypi.org/project/vcd/>). The second step in this stage is the so-called Semantic Augmentation, which reads the object-level information, in the form of OpenLabel labels, and augment their content with additional measurements, which can be directly derived from the presence, position, volume or

other labels of the objects presents in the scene. For instance, collision or other proximity-related metrics like Time-To-Collision can be computed at this stage. Such content fills-in the semantic gaps of object-level labels in preparation for more advanced semantic inference in subsequent stages.

At the database stage, content is unwrapped from its OpenLabel format and decomposed into a data model in a Graph database. In particular, we propose to use GraphDB, and as such we are using a data model specified by an ontology which is loaded into GraphDB as a set of nodes and relations, specifying the classes and properties of the elements as defined by the OpenLabel schema.

The query manager is the component responsible for loading search queries into the database, and thus, retrieve found content under specific rules. In our approach, a search query can execute a semantic inference rule. For instance, a lane-change maneuver can be defined as a sequence of related events, including relations that identify a vehicle located in a certain lane, and in a posterior instant, located in an adjacent lane. Additional control instructions can narrow down the specification of the rule, in order to find only the specified sequence if happen in specific positions (e.g., in front of the ego-vehicle), or during specific periods of time. Concatenation of such Resource Description Framework (RDF) triplets can lead to the definition of rules as complex as desired, and then unlimited level of semantic complexity of the scenario of interest.

The creation of the queries can be created with a web application as interface, where an expert can write down the rule in a certain query-specific language. This process is understood in this context as scenario mining activity, although the same process can be used to inject content into the database as any created query can not only search content but also create content.

It is important to highlight that the governing ontology shall be applied coherently at all levels (data preparation, database and search application), so that all terms are mapped, and no semantic inconsistencies exist. This way, the semantic layer guarantees that all relations between classes are bounded to the specified semantic domain, and all inference will lead to the desired results.

Additional visualization tools can be used to monitorize the produced content. For instance, it is possible to use the WebLabel tool by Vicomtech to visualize raw data along with ASAM OpenLabel labels (including object-level labels and semantic labels).

Use case 2.2: Robust prediction modules for robo-taxis in urban environment

The figure below showcases the block diagram for the demonstrator 2.2, followed by an overview of specific steps to be performed to demonstrate the use case overall.

Figure 25: Block diagram: Robust prediction modules for Robo-taxi environments

Figure 26: Information flow of prediction based on environmental awareness.

In UC-2.2, the initial task is to create real-world data for training and validating machine learning models. This process includes collecting data using a dedicated data acquisition system, performing filtering and cleaning, and visualizing the data. By doing so, the scenarios, operational design domains (ODDs), and sensor configurations in which the machine learning model will be evaluated, is established. This step is crucial for determining the model’s capabilities and operating conditions.

A methodology incorporating X-in-the-loop will be developed to effectively bridge the gap between virtual and physical testing environments. Given the constrained person months available in the AITHENA project, the strategy will involve setting up for Vehicle-in-the-Loop (ViL) testing and ensuring a functional Drive-By-Wire system for future integration with ML-based controllers. The

primary goal is to assess the vehicle's response to a controller that utilizes data generated from Simcenter Prescan and to evaluate the deployment of the developed machine learning model on an Electronic Control Unit (ECU) in real-time. The model will undergo testing to identify performance deficiencies across a comprehensive range of driving scenarios (outlined by partners in Task 2.1). These include challenges like inadequate object detection, tracking, trajectory estimation, and issues with false negatives and positives in predictions. The validation methodology is designed to ensure that the acceptance criteria are met with a robust level of confidence. Additionally, thorough data analysis will be carried out to investigate the defined requirements, environmental conditions, and triggers for the model's misbehaviour. Reports will be prepared to pinpoint the root causes of potential failures in the machine learning model, such as the algorithm's failure to accurately represent the surrounding environment. The acceptance criteria for validating the model will focus on the probability of the machine learning model being uncontrollable in specified scenarios, the severity of accidents during these tests, and the incidence of behaviours leading to unforeseen outcomes.

The process of data acquisition, perception, sensor fusion, environmental modelling, and prediction for situational awareness creates a computational chain. System virtualization and/or containerization, along with a shared middleware, support the independent development and testing of software components within this chain. The use case employs ROS2 as a middleware for facilitating communication among independently developed components and uses Docker containers to encapsulate ROS2 applications that constitute a software component. The accuracy of a computational chain is influenced not just by the accuracy of its computational results but also by the promptness of these computations. The timing requirements for a computational chain—such as how often it runs and the deadline for delivering new computational results—are governed by the demands of the real-world process.

This timing data for containerized software components, which includes their execution period, deadline, and worst-case execution time (WCET), is utilized to generate an offline schedule prior to integrating the components on the embedded platform. Running such a schedule ensures the timing accuracy of the computational chain. The task of creating a scheduling solution for these components across a predetermined number of embedded platforms presents an NP-complete problem, which is complex to solve but straightforward to verify post-generation for correctness. To guarantee the accuracy of these schedules during the design phase, it is crucial to first establish constraints for the scheduling hierarchy driven by time-triggered container execution and the ROS2 instances managing application scheduling within each container. Additionally, containerized software components within the situational awareness computational chain have data dependencies, where the output from one component serves as the input for one or more subsequent components. Ultimately, this situational awareness computational chain is responsible for monitoring real-world events that determine the end-to-end latency of the computation, defined as the maximum duration from data acquisition by the first software component to the generation of a prediction by the last component.

Assuming the perception system's output is integrated with existing map data, an environmental model can be established, allowing for the prediction of movements of traffic participants. Each cycle of the perception system, enriched by the task of object-level data fusion, is designed to be completed

in real time to maintain continuous traffic situation awareness. Yet, situational awareness involves more than merely gathering data on the traffic scenario—it includes interpreting the links between diverse information sources. A robust situational awareness framework would, for instance, need to establish connections between each update of a traffic participant's status and the existing road infrastructure. These connections might also be semantic, linking individual traffic participants in meaningful ways. Thus, identifying a comprehensive set of these relationships can significantly enhance the understanding of the overall traffic situation.

Once an understanding of the traffic situation is established, it can be converted into a format that the motion prediction model can interpret. This reformatted input is then utilized to predict potential trajectories for each detected traffic participant. For the predictions to be accurate, it is crucial that comprehensive traffic data, both observed and deduced, are integrated from the environment model to the prediction model's input. This process introduces an observational bias, meaning the model and its predictions are conditioned based on the data provided during its training phase. However, the reliability of these predictions cannot be assured by observational bias alone (Karniadakis et al. 2021). The model must also incorporate constraints derived from prior knowledge, such as physical laws, which can influence the model's structure and learning algorithm—referred to as inductive bias and learning bias, respectively.

Developing a model with these biases aligns with AITHENA's overarching aim to enhance the explainability of the models used. Making the operations of what was previously a black-box model more comprehensible to developers also makes the explanations provided to users more credible. Therefore, the selection of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) must adhere to the accuracy and feasibility required for the safe and effective navigation of a robo-taxi. These indicators should consider the specifics of the urban environment where the robo-taxi operates, such as the prediction time horizon and information about navigable areas. This approach ensures that the model remains practical and reliable in real-world conditions.

Key technologies/AI-based models

Use case 2.1: Collision prediction with hybrid AI data fusion

This use case aims to produce a component, the SLS, which is not AI-based, but that can be used in the context of the evaluation of AI models. The key technologies for this use case are:

- Graphical databases: a database that structures information as graphs, and enables execution of semantic queries. E.g., Neo4j, GraphDB.
- Semantic Query Language: a language that permits the construction of rules as queries, to be run as logical inference queries against the graphical database. E.g., SPARQL, Cypher.
- Ontologies: abstract constructs that define classes, properties and relationships, materializing a data model. Ontologies can be created with semantic languages like OWL or RDF.

Use case 2.2: Robust prediction modules for robo-taxis in urban environment

The AI-based Situational Awareness Feature Enhanced Object Detection (SAFEOD) functionality is used in UC2.2. The prediction model development will be based on the SFM methodology proposed in the studies by Cui et al. (2020), Chou et al. (2020) and Hong et al. (2019).

The UC2.2 develops a sophisticated algorithmic framework for advanced perception in autonomous vehicles. This framework is crucial for the reliable operation of robo-taxis, ensuring they can effectively detect objects, identify free space, and recognize lane boundaries. This is a fundamental step before predicting lane changes, which is essential for situational awareness and safety in complex urban environments. To provide a clear understanding of the perception system, distinct algorithms and their sensor-based functionalities are explained as follows:

- The Object Detection algorithm relies on data from both the frontal camera and LIDAR. Frontal cameras provide high-resolution images that are essential for recognizing and classifying various objects such as vehicles, pedestrians, and other elements in the vehicle's visual field. LIDAR complements this by providing depth information.
- The Lane Detection algorithm is primarily based on frontal camera data. These cameras capture road markings and lanes, and the algorithm processes these images to delineate the current lane structure. This information is critical for maintaining the robo-taxi within its lane and for executing safe lane changes, as it establishes a reference for the vehicle's positioning on the road.
- The Free Space Detection algorithm uses LIDAR data processed through the ROS2 Foxy framework. This algorithm, which relies on the dataset provided by Siemens, receives input in the form of a standard point cloud, as defined by ROS2's official format. Its output, `FreespaceOutput.msg` enables the algorithm to deliver a multi-dimensional understanding of the vehicle's surroundings, critical for the safe navigation and operational efficiency of autonomous robo-taxis in complex urban landscapes.
- The Data Fusion algorithm synthesizes the information gathered by both cameras and LIDAR. This algorithm ensures that object and lane detection data are not considered in isolation; instead, it creates a unified environmental model that the lane change prediction system can use.

The Lane Change Prediction algorithm is a vital component that synthesizes all the data gathered from the previous algorithms — object detection, lane detection, and free space detection. Its primary role is to predict when vehicles are likely to change lanes. In fact, by analysing the comprehensive environmental model generated by the Data Fusion algorithm, the Lane Change Prediction algorithm can anticipate potential movements of other vehicles. This foresight is critical for the robo-taxi's decision-making process, enabling it to adjust its course or speed proactively to avoid collisions and ensure a safe driving experience. Therefore, this prediction is crucial for the autonomous vehicle's safety and smooth operation in busy urban environments. In conclusion, the framework aims to enhance the safety and efficiency of robo-taxis in urban settings aligning with AITHENA's purposes.

Each algorithm — from Object Detection and Lane Detection to Free Space Detection and Data Fusion — plays a specific role in creating a detailed and accurate understanding of the vehicle's surroundings and results in the development of the Lane Change Prediction algorithm, a crucial component that brings together all the processed data to anticipate and react to dynamic traffic conditions.

Scope and restrictions

Use case 2.1: Collision prediction with hybrid AI data fusion

The use case will be limited to a certain ontology, considering a limited number of types of edge cases. Considering the scope are AI-models for collision prediction, the following actions are expected to be semantically modelled:

- Hard braking Scenario: Rapid deceleration of a vehicle.
- Hard acceleration Scenario: Rapid acceleration of a vehicle.
- Lane changing: Ego vehicle changing lanes.
- Pedestrian crossing: Pedestrian crossing the lane.
- Cut in: Vehicle suddenly moves out of its lane, cutting off the ego vehicle and causing the latter to brake abruptly.
- Cut out: Vehicle abruptly merges into a lane directly in front the ego vehicle, causing the latter to potentially brake or adjust speed to maintain a safe following distance.
- Overtaking: Vehicle accelerates and moves into an adjacent lane to pass the ego vehicle traveling in the same direction, then returns to the original lane.
- Over speeding: Vehicle exceeds the posted speed limit or drives at a speed that is unsafe for the current road.
- Car following: Vehicle following the ego vehicle.
- Near miss collision: Vehicle getting too close to the ego vehicle, often requiring sudden braking or lane changes.

In addition, the use case requires the existence of accurately labelled datasets which are large enough to contain some of the target edge-cases. A priori, the nuScenes (<https://www.nuscenes.org/>) dataset seems to gather all the requirements.

Use case 2.2: Robust prediction modules for robo-taxis in urban environment

The scope of UC2.2 is clear on the scene understanding task. This means no decisions based on the understood scene are within the scope of UC2.2. The urban environment in which the module is expected to generate accurate and robust motion predictions is characterized by the different traffic participants interacting with each other and their surroundings. Since the environment and scenarios unfolding in it can be described at different abstraction levels, we will focus on the level that recognizes different classes of traffic participants, segments of road infrastructure with corresponding traffic rules, and specific surrounding objects (e.g., buildings) as individual scenario elements. These elements can be then translated into the format that can be used as input to the prediction module. Additionally, some characteristics specific to the scenarios will be considered edge cases and will reflect on the definition of the scope of the UC2.2 and, consequently, the scope of the prediction module.

Among the traffic participants that can be observed in an urban environment, special attention will be placed on vulnerable road users (VRUs) such as pedestrians and cyclists. While the prediction of vehicle motion (e.g., personal vehicles, buses) is a challenging task in its own right, the volatility of the pedestrians' motion poses even more challenges. The reasons behind this volatility are often social (walking in a group, stopping in front of a store) and as such can hardly be observed by the perception module. Therefore, such social effects can only be considered by the prediction module through priors that are integrated into the module design.

It is assumed that the prediction module will have access to map information of the urban area enriched with information on the type of road segments (e.g., road, sidewalk, or crossing segments) or road structures (e.g., T or four-way intersections). Additionally, the traffic rules that follow from such road segments (e.g., the possibility of changing lanes) or structures (e.g., right-of-way rules) will be referenced as priors of the module. These rules could be further modified or overwritten depending on the availability of traffic signs and signalization information for the considered area. Given the limited representation of scenarios in which the traffic flow is regulated by a police officer, such scenarios will not be included in the UC2.2 scope. It should be noted that certain occurrences of traffic rule violation will be introduced to the module (e.g., pedestrians moving near road crossings), but further analysis of more severe cases will be left out of the UC2.2 scope.

While the scope encompasses a variety of road segments and structures, their condition is assumed to be ideal, i.e., the module can know of closed-off segments (e.g., construction zones) only if such information is provided during the training stage. Other environmental factors, such as adverse weather conditions, that can affect the perception, and consequently, the prediction module's performance are also not considered. To avoid performance reduction caused by poor visibility during nighttime, the prediction module will be trained and tested only on the scenarios taking place during the daytime.

Finally, the prediction module will not be tasked with resolving certain edge cases, but rather it will be assumed that these cases are resolved by the perception module. Information on the occluded traffic participants or signs is to be provided by the perception module should such cases occur. Similarly, the perception module should inform the prediction module of traffic participants that may be present in the robo-taxi's blind spots. Therefore, with the assumption that the perception module provides traffic participants' states even in these edge cases, they will be considered by the prediction module directly.

Scenarios/use case story for CCAM applications

Use case 2.1: Collision prediction with hybrid AI data fusion

The proposed approach will be exercised with urban scenarios, including interactions between pedestrians and vehicles, especially those related to potentially risky situations, such as zebra-crossing situations, pedestrians partially occluded by parked cars, etc. In addition, non-urban environments will also be considered to include (mostly) interactions between vehicles, with classical scenarios cut-in, cut-out, hard-brake, etc., as described in previous sections.

Use case 2.2: Robust prediction modules for robo-taxis in urban environment

Scenarios set in an urban environment can often be characterized by the diversity of traffic participants whose motion is influenced by various scenario elements such as other traffic participants, road infrastructure, or traffic rules. Therefore, particular interest is taken in the scenarios in which each traffic participant is simultaneously subjected to different types of interactions. This includes single and multi-lane urban intersection scenarios involving trucks, cars, motorbikes, cyclists, and pedestrians as traffic participants.

An illustrative scenario presenting the complexities of the urban environment is the scenario considering different traffic participants at an intersection crossing. The module is expected to accurately predict the motion of each participant, focusing on vulnerable road users (VRUs) like pedestrians or cyclists, while respecting the intersection structure and traffic rules. The accuracy, robustness, and feasibility of predictions in such complex scenarios depend on the sources of scenario information and how it is introduced to the model. To enhance understanding of how inputs impact predictions, the model integrates explainable approaches at different component levels. These not only reveal the model's inner workings but also enable generalization across previously unknown inputs. Therefore, explainable approaches allow for the utilization of extensive prior knowledge both to guide the model's design and development and subsequently inform the model of the observed scenarios.

4.2.3. Requirements

Functional data requirements

Use case 2.1: Collision prediction with hybrid AI data fusion

- Semantic Labeling System (SLS) shall be able to load an ontology
- SLE shall be able to run logical inference queries
- Logical inference queries shall be writable as expert rules and be human-readable
- The ontology shall contain actions related to collision prediction, such as hard braking scenario, hard acceleration scenario, lane changing, pedestrian crossing, cut in, cut out, overtaking, over speeding, car following, and near miss collision
- An open dataset with object-level annotations shall be used, which contains some of the edge cases.
- The dataset shall be converted to OpenLabel 1.0.0 format
- The resulting detected edge cases by the SLS shall be writable using OpenLabel 1.0.0 format

Use case 2.2: Robust prediction modules for robo-taxis in urban environment

- Based on the information flow in the U2.2 functional description, considering data acquisition step dataset generation will be performed in accordance with requirements (vehicle setup, scenario types, ODDs) specified by involved partners.
- The SAFEOD function block shall detect:
 1. dynamic objects such as trucks, cars, motorbikes, bicycles, and pedestrians.

2. static objects of type traffic light, including the current active traffic light colour.
 3. activated vehicle signal lights of type brake and left/right turn indicators related to dynamic objects of type car.
 4. bounding box orientation of dynamic objects of type car and truck.
- The prediction module shall:
 1. incorporate one or multiple design components to enhance the explainability of the overall model.
 2. provide accurate, feasible and robust trajectory predictions for a variety of urban traffic scenarios.
 3. provide long-term horizon predictions of traffic participant's trajectories.
 4. aggregate heterogeneous scenario data provided by multiple data sources (e.g. prediction system, traffic management system, map information)
 - Use of ROS2 as middleware for communication between independently developed components and Docker containers to package ROS2 applications that form a software component.

Operational / performance requirements

Use case 2.1: Collision prediction with hybrid AI data fusion

For UC2.1 as a performance requirement, the SLS shall not produce a False Positive Rate (FPR) higher than 10%-

Use case 2.2: Robust prediction modules for robo-taxis in urban environment

For UC 2.2, the operational requirement is to establish initial criteria for validating simulation accuracy against real-world data and verifying the simulated vehicle's behaviour against reality.

Legal requirements

Use case 2.1: Collision prediction with hybrid AI data fusion

Openly available datasets, properly anonymized shall be used for the UC 2.1.

Use case 2.2: Robust prediction modules for robo-taxis in urban environment

Considering the information flow of prediction based on environmental awareness, dedicated real-world datasets will be shared according to the Siemens GDPR guidelines with the involved partners for labelling the datasets and further refining automatically generated annotations using pretrained machine learning models.

Usability and human interaction requirements

Use case 2.1: Collision prediction with hybrid AI data fusion

Considering UC 2.1, the rules shall be human-readable for users of type test engineers. In addition, the rules shall be extensible to controlled natural language to be human-readable by non-technical stakeholders.

Use case 2.2: Robust prediction modules for robo-taxis in urban environment

It is expected of the robo-taxi's interaction with its users (i.e., passengers) to include display of information regarding the surrounding environmental information (impacting robo-taxi's decision making). Considering interaction with the vulnerable road users like pedestrians or cyclists, the use case will address the information to the user-group of its presence. The robo-taxi should provide some form of signalling to the surrounding traffic participants.

4.3. Trustworthy and human-understandable decision making

4.3.1. Strategy

Rationale

Referring to the trustworthiness of automated driving systems the accuracy and robustness of each module in the pipeline are important. Since the vehicle guidance system builds up on information of the upstream modules (namely perception and situation awareness) while at the same time being the last module in the pipeline, the reason why, when, and how a decision is taken plays a major role, especially for occupants of the vehicle.

This use case titled 'Trustworthy and Human understandable decision making' is related to the task of vehicle guidance in an automated driving system. It refers to the last major task in the pipeline and is responsible for interpreting the provided information on the surrounding environment, to derive reasonable decisions from this. This is also referred to as motion planning, in which algorithms usually provide a trajectory of future vehicle states. Using various control algorithms, scalar values like longitudinal acceleration and a steering angle can be derived. These values are provided to the vehicle actuators so that the vehicle follows the pre-planned trajectory properly.

Objectives

The focus of this use case and the corresponding demonstrator is to explain decisions to the user of the system before, while, or after they have been executed. Next to this, trustworthiness should be increased by providing a robust system, that is capable of handling situations understandably, even if the present situation confronts the vehicle with unforeseen circumstances. The main objectives of this use case are:

- Integration of an explainable AI interface into the relevant algorithms for decision making to visualize and explain decisions before, while or after they are executed.

- Increasing robustness of a vehicle guidance system through competence observation of algorithms responsible for decision making.
- Demonstration of the explainable AI interface and competence observation in reasonable scenarios.

Approach

Implementation of the Use-Case will be tackled through a sequential approach of two cycles according to the AITHENA methodology: In Cycle 1 development, testing and demonstration will take place using various simulative approaches. In Cycle 2 the implemented algorithms will be integrated, improved, and applied to a real-world demonstrator vehicle. The actual demonstration will take place on a closed test track.

The use case objectives will be tackled through the integration of an explainable AI interface in the relevant algorithms for motion planning on the one hand, and by the implementation and integration of a separate module, that measures the competence of AI algorithms in the motion planning stack. To demonstrate the capabilities of the explainable AI interface the use case will focus on a scenario, that causes the vehicle to behave in a way, that is not intuitive for the occupant and therefore requires an additional explanation. The use case will therefore focus on V2X information which are not perceivable for the occupant directly (see scenario).

Secondly, the capabilities of competence observation are demonstrated through a scenario that represents an unforeseen situation for the implemented motion planning algorithms. An example for this can be the passing of a roundabout (see scenario). The roundabout will represent an unforeseen situation, in case the training dataset used to train the data-driven motion planning module does not contain any samples with roundabout situations. The implementation of the demonstrated algorithms is carried out within the scope of WP3, more precisely in Task 3.5. For the development and testing of these algorithms, simulation environments and scenarios will be used in an initial phase, which will be developed as part of WP4. Furthermore, data sets provided through WP2 may be used for the development of corresponding ML models. Finally, the integration of the developed algorithms in simulation scenarios as well as demonstrator vehicles is carried out as part of WP5. In addition, a testing and validation methodology is developed as part of WP5. Requirements, test scenarios and evaluation metrics will be defined to evaluate the algorithms and methods developed for the realisation of this use case.

Challenges and risk

- Integration of data driven approaches for motion planning into a vehicle guidance system: The use of data-driven approaches poses a particular challenge for decision-making and motion planning, as this has a significant influence on the behaviour of the vehicle. In particular, the lack of traceability of such approaches poses challenges for the developers and users of such systems. We counter this by combining the data-driven approaches with a subsequent, rule-based validation of the proposed behavioural decision.

- Domain shift from virtual- to real-world-scenario: As with all data-driven approaches, the transferability of the algorithms from the test and development environment to the real world is a challenge in development. Since the input data of the corresponding approaches are abstracted in our case, the domain shift at this point may be smaller than, for example, with algorithms for perception where there are greater differences in the representation of the input data for training, testing and validation compared to the real sensor data. Nevertheless, data-driven approaches to decision making and motion planning pose specific challenges. For example, deviations from the planned manoeuvre may occur due to inaccuracies in vehicle control, which are not represented in the training data.
- Generation of representative datasets for the training of data driven approaches for motion planning: A key challenge for data-driven approaches in the context of automated driving is the availability of representative datasets. However, no ready-to-use products are being developed and presented as part of this project, so there is no requirement for a complete and representative data set to be available. Rather, the data is chosen deliberately to be able to demonstrate the concepts presented in a targeted way (i.e. refer to Scenario 2).
- Breakdown of Demonstrator Vehicle: Breakdown or limited functionality of the demonstrator vehicle due to unforeseen problems is possible. In case, the implemented modules cannot be demonstrated in a closed-loop manner, meaning that the system is controlling the vehicle controls, an open-loop demonstration of the implemented functionality is possible. In case of a total vehicle breakdown, demonstration of the implemented functionality can be demonstrated using a static demonstrator with pre-recorded real-world data in an open-loop manner.

4.3.2. Solution

Functional description

The process of vehicle guidance is typically divided into three distinct tasks: navigation, guidance, and stabilization (Donges 1982). Functionally, these tasks operate in sequence, where the output from the navigation, typically a planned route within a road network, serves as the input for the guidance level algorithms. The output from these guidance algorithms is often a trajectory that predicts future vehicle states. Subsequently, algorithms at the stabilization level use this trajectory to compute scalar control values, which are then transmitted to the vehicle's actuators. By activating these actuators, the vehicle is steered along the designated trajectory. Alongside this sequential operation, the generation of routes, decision-making on behaviour, trajectory planning, and vehicle control adjustments are performed in a cyclical manner, with the frequency of recalculations generally increasing from navigation to stabilization. The different algorithms acting on the specific levels of vehicle guidance use different approaches like graph- and tree-search, numerical optimization, deep neural networks, or different control techniques like model-predictive-control. Consequently, the input and output formats, as well as the optimization goals, differ across these algorithms. Nevertheless, the primary objectives of the vehicle guidance system remain consistent: optimizing comfort, efficiency, and safety.

The implementation of such a system for automated vehicle guidance as demonstrated in this use case is illustrated on the right-hand side of the figure below. The *Global Route Planning* module generates a global route leading the vehicle from its current position to a desired destination. This route is fed into the *Local Environment Model*, which is responsible for two tasks. First it gathers and fuses all available information provided through the modules of onboard perception, received over external V2X communication, or derived from map data. Secondly the fused information is provided to the underlying modules according to their requirements on the input representation. The first planning instance, namely the *Tactical Decision Making* requires the environment information represented like a multi-layered bird's eye view image. Each layer in this image describes different information categories in the local vehicle environment, such as dynamic objects like vehicles and pedestrians or information about the road. The neural network predicts a vehicle trajectory based on the given input. As this trajectory is very discrete and not necessarily verified in terms of driving physics, it is processed in a further step by the *Trajectory Optimization & Supervision* module to ensure the driveability and compliance to rudimentary traffic regulations. This module also provides a vehicle trajectory that is passed to underlying control algorithms and the actuators so that the vehicle properly follows the planned trajectory.

Figure 27: Abstracted functional architecture of software modules demonstrated in UC3

In addition to the actual vehicle guidance system, the flowchart above also shows the abstracted architecture of the competence observation on the left-hand side. This module is based on the same data set as the *Tactical Decision Making*. In addition, information about the underlying situation is provided at runtime through the *Local Environment Model*. This information is used to determine a competence measure for the underlying situation. This measure is used through the *Trajectory Optimization & Supervision* to estimate the confidence of the trajectory generated by the Deep-Learning-based (DL-based) *Tactical Decision Making* and initiate suitable actions in situations with low competence.

Key technologies/AI-based models

The main contribution of this use case is the Hybrid-AI Motion Planning stack on the one hand and a module for observing the competence of the implemented software stack in different traffic situations on the other hand. The implemented Hybrid AI system for motion planning is based on Deep Learning as well as subsequent hard-coded rules to achieve a robust overall system. Thus, it shows a combination of learning-based and “classical” approaches. Competence Observation is mainly based on a knowledge graph, modelling the relationship between different entities, in this case with respect to the context of the environment of an automated vehicle.

Scope and restrictions

The scope of this use case is the demonstration of the modules developed in WP3. The demonstrated scenario focus on the explanation of the systems decisions before, while or after they have been executed. In addition, the implemented system tries to increase, trustworthiness by providing a robust system, that is capable in handling situations, even if the present situation confronts the vehicle with unforeseen circumstances.

Regarding the explanation of the decision-making about the driving behaviour, the use case will focus on the implementation and the provisioning of interfaces on the software level, e.g. for the visualisation of information about the planned and executed driving behaviour. This will be demonstrated using exemplary visualisations. The investigation of when and how the information is necessary and useful for passengers is not part of this use case. Furthermore, it will not investigate which form of information presentation (language, visualisation, text...) is most suitable for the different user groups (children, adults, elderly people, people with disabilities...) of automated vehicles. Nevertheless, the results can be transferred to other forms of presentation in the future. Furthermore, the results of this use case are not limited to specific types of automated vehicles: the results can be applied to any form of automated mobility (cars, personal transport, robo-taxis etc.).

Regarding the observation of the competence of an DL-based decision-making module, the use case will focus on recognising situations and contexts in which the competence of the model is low. The vehicle should react to this information in an exemplary manner. Researching which action is most suitable is not within the scope of this use case. With reference to the next subsection, this use case will focus on urban scenarios. Especially highway scenarios are out of scope of this use case.

In conclusion, the proposed scenarios mainly address the occupants of automated vehicles as a target group. Nevertheless, the explanation of the decisions also assists developers, testers, and regulatory authorities. Related to the AI lifecycle this demonstrator mainly addresses the post deployment phase and more precisely the operational use of AI systems in CCAM. Nevertheless, also the redeployment and monitoring are addressed. For example, the demonstrated software stack can identify scenarios for which the DL-based trajectory planning has not been trained. This information can be used, to initiate a targeted retraining and redeployment of the corresponding algorithms.

Scenarios/use case story for CCAM applications

The use case will demonstrate specific scenarios that target the explanation of non-intuitive situations on the one hand, and the robustness against unknown contexts and situations on the other hand. We will demonstrate two scenarios that are described as follows:

Scenario 1: Explanation of non-intuitive braking due to occluded vehicle

The Ego vehicle (blue) is approaching a junction with a green traffic light. Nevertheless, the vehicle decelerates which unsettles the occupant because it shows non-intuitive behaviour for the occupant. The system will explain to the occupant, that it slowed down because it received information via V2X, about an occluded vehicle (turquoise) that violates a red traffic light.

Figure 28: Schematic illustration of Scenario 1 for UC3

Scenario 2: Robustness of Hybrid AI planning stack against unknown contexts

The Ego vehicle is approaching a roundabout. Since roundabouts are not part of the dataset that was used to train the DL-based *Tactical Decision Making*, it might fail in predicting a reasonable trajectory. Through *Competence Observation* the lower competence in this situation is measured and provided to the Trajectory Supervision module. In this case the *Trajectory Optimization & Supervision* will rely less on the DL-based decision and instead initiate an alternative trajectory to safely guide the vehicle around the roundabout.

Figure 29: Schematic illustration for Scenario 2 for UC3

4.3.3. Requirements

Functional & data requirements

Considering the functional and scenario description, the set of requirements are listed as follows:

Req. 1: Following a route to a given destination

The vehicle follows a given route from the current vehicle position to a given destination.

Req. 2: Lateral vehicle movement is controlled through the software stack

The implemented vehicle guidance system can keep the vehicle within its respective driving lane along the route.

Req. 3: Longitudinal vehicle movement is controlled through the software stack

The implemented vehicle guidance system can adjust the vehicle speed according to the vehicle environment.

Req. 4: Reception of V2X Information

The vehicle can receive, and process specified V2X information. More specific the following message types should be processed: Cooperative Awareness Message (CAM)

Req. 5: Taking into account CAM provided from other vehicles

The vehicle considers Cooperative Awareness Messages provided through other vehicles in the surrounding. If a potential collision is detected, the vehicle will decelerate or come to a standstill.

Req. 6: Information received via V2X communication are visualized for the occupant

Especially V2X information are not directly perceivable for the occupant of the vehicle. To explain the vehicle behaviour based on V2X information to the occupant, the additional knowledge should be made accessible to the occupant through visualisation.

Req. 7: Training data for DL-based Tactical Decision Making

To demonstrate the capabilities of the *Competence Observation* module it is required that the dataset does not contain training samples with roundabouts.

Req. 8: *Competence Observation* is able to measure the competence of the DL-based *Tactical Decision Making*

The *Competence Observation* can measure the competence of the DL-based *Tactical Decision Making* based on the context the vehicle is located in. This use case will focus on roundabout scenarios as unknown context.

Req. 9: Consideration of competence indication in vehicle guidance system

The implemented vehicle guidance system considers the competence indication provided by the *Competence Observation* module. The system will decrease the trust in the predicted trajectory provided by the DL-based *Tactical Decision Making*. However, to provide a robust overall system, an alternative trajectory is initiated and used to guide the vehicle safely until the competence of the DL-based *Tactical Decision-Making* module is assessed as sufficiently high again.

Operational / performance requirements

As proposed by the described scenarios the use case requires an ODD with urban junctions equipped with traffic lights and buildings leading to occlusion, as well as roundabouts in an urban environment. The overall goal is to develop a robust system in these defined circumstances. Potential measures for the performance in these scenarios are the ability of the vehicle to stay in its respective lane while following a given route. Moreover, the system should guide the vehicle in a way that it considers a sufficient distance to other vehicles and especially vulnerable road users (VRUs).

Legal requirements

To train data-driven behaviour models, corresponding behavioural data from human drivers are required, representing the desired driving behaviour the model should learn from. Such data contain information about the location and time as well as the corresponding behaviour of a person in a specific situation. The data should be processed and recorded in such a way that it does not allow any conclusions to be drawn about individual person.

Useability and human interaction requirements

As described above, one objective of this Use-Case is to integrate “an explainable AI interface into the relevant algorithms for decision making to visualize and explain decisions before, while or after they are executed”. Thus, the Use-Case requires interaction with human beings, more specific in form of human-machine interaction inside of the vehicle. But as describe in the section about the scope of the use-case, research on the design of this internal HMI (Human-Machine-Interface) is not part of the use case. In contrast, the use case focuses on the general question of how relevant information can be provided, particularly from data-driven algorithms, to enable corresponding HMIs.

4.4. AI-based Traffic Management

4.4.1. Strategy

Rationale

At the transport-level, applications such as traffic management (TM) interact with AI-based systems running at the vehicle-level. On the one hand, the Automated vehicles (AVs) currently behave differently than vehicles driven by humans and therefore can impact the traffic dynamics on the network level in unexpected ways. On the other hand, TM systems can impact AVs to support situational awareness, path planning and manoeuvre decision making, especially, when data cannot be obtained by vehicle sensors and maps but is exclusively available through TM systems (i.e., local roadside equipment (V2X) and/or cloud services (e.g., road operator, digital twin / DATEX II)).

On top of this, the response of systems (i.e., TM systems and ADS in AVs) and drivers depends on the level of trust they have in information from other systems and/or the capabilities of AVs in general. The level of trust determines to what extent systems take such information into account and to what extent drivers are likely to adjust their behaviour.

So, while in theory most complex situations (i.e., edge cases) can be overcome by providing sufficient information in a timely manner, this is only true when there is a high level of trust in that information. In practice, the level of trust varies depending on experience or training of humans and machine learning algorithms.

Increasing the trustworthiness in the capabilities of AVs by evaluating the interaction with other systems and drivers is important to road operators and traffic managers to assure information shared and effectiveness of measures reached, to manage traffic on their road network. In addition, studying the impact of these interactions on the network level makes it more transparent what it means to introduce AVs in a network. The evaluations in this use case demonstrate the effect of the level of trust has on network level KPI's focused on efficiency, safety and sustainability. Using different penetration rates of AVs and different levels of trust, the results can be used as a knowledge base to assess what the impact is when a certain percentage of AVs is introduced in a city, given an estimation of the level of trust in the capabilities of that type of AV and the level of trust that type of AV has in information from other systems.

To this end, the goal is to understand to what extent this level of trust impacts the traffic dynamics at the transport system level. By understanding the causality between this trust and impact (at the transport system level), trustworthiness (refer to D1.1) is gained from a traffic management perspective. To assess that causality at the transport system level, one needs to focus on a network rather than single or a few vehicles because the impact can be minor when considering the behaviour of a single vehicle or more substantial due to the cumulative effect of a small deviation in the behaviour of multiple vehicles.

Objectives

Following AITHENA's XAI approach, the UC aims to increase the trustworthiness of the AI of AVs from a traffic management perspective. To do that, the impact of that AI on the traffic dynamics on the network level must be transparent. This transparency is gained by understanding in what way the network level performance is impacted by introducing AVs in the network. Considering this, the primary objective of the use case is to understand the causality between the AI behaviour of AVs and the network performance in terms of efficiency, safety, and sustainability.

The causality can only be understood if there is some reference the performance can be compared to. In addition, the AI of AVs can be supported by additional information from outside sources such as V2X information from traffic management or some dedicated information channel from a fleet management solution. Therefore, in addition to the primary objective, there are two sub-objectives:

- Define a benchmark/reference for desired/acceptable behaviour and/or minimal driving performance expectations (e.g., based on codified rules of the road)
- Analyse the response of AI-models to traffic management data, at strategic, tactical, and operational levels (which may help vehicles to monitor the status of ODD attributes and handling conditions needing outside information).

Approach

While the other AITHENA use cases focus on part of the AI of a single vehicle (i.e., perception, situational awareness, and decision-making), use case 4 focusses on the impact of AI on the network level from a traffic management perspective. Since AITHENA does not have an entire real-life network for testing at its disposal, use case 4 predominantly take a virtual approach for the two cycles of the AITHENA project. Using microsimulation, the interactions between different types of vehicles can be studied and the traffic dynamics can be evaluated at the network/macrosopic level. That evaluation focuses on efficiency, safety, and sustainability. This way, the impact of the introduction of AVs in the network becomes more transparent and by extension the trustworthiness of the AVs.

For the first AITHENA cycle, the goal is to setup a microsimulation using the VISSIM (Sukennik & Kautzsch 2018) software that can be used to simulate a traffic network. An incident, particularly challenging for an AV, shall be part of the simulation to evaluate the impact of the AV response to that incident on the network level. The AV response depends on traffic management information about how to handle the incident and the AV's trust in that information. In case traffic management information is available and the AV trusts the TM information, the AV can overcome the situation. If not, the AV is not able to overcome the situation and some amount of time pass by until a backup system (e.g., handover, remote control, remote guidance, etc.) helps the vehicle to overcome the situation.

During the second AITHENA cycle, the results of the other AITHENA use cases will be evaluated to determine if specific AV behaviours can be identified that deviate from the behaviour of other vehicles. Those behaviours will then be included in the simulation to evaluate the network-wide

effects. In addition, other types of situations of particular interest to traffic management can be introduced and evaluated. Finally, other traffic compositions can be explored as well as other network configurations. Which variations/expansions will be explored during the second cycle will depend on the ongoing results.

Challenges and risk

Based on the rationale, the objectives and the approaches of UC₄, several challenges related to find the causality between AI model and macroscopic traffic effects, and the transparency and predictability of that causality in a microscopic simulation software were identified:

- To design and set up UC₄ in a complex large-scale urban network, choosing the edge cases that best capture the decision making, interactions of non-AVs and AVs and response to TM messages, is the first challenge. Therefore, UC₄ chose to set up a proof-of-concept design of overtaking a break-down vehicle using opposite lane, assuming that distinct decision-making processes of non-AVs, AV-with-trust, AV-without-trust are most likely to occur.
- It is difficult to capture/identify the delta behaviours among non-AVs, AV-with-trust, AV-without-trust in UC₄, especially in edge cases on a large-scale network. The driving behaviour competencies of AVs and non-AVs exhibit similarities, which arises from the AI designs of the AVs conforming to the current traffic laws and regulations, as well as the Rules of The Road (ROTRs). While human driving patterns are heterogenous and unpredictable, to what extent the AI designs follow the human driving patterns is difficult to measure and up to each OEM to configure, especially under edge cases. This presents significant challenges to capture the behavioural discrepancies of non-AVs and AVs in the busy urban network of UC₄ with complex traffic signs and signals.
- In UC₄, the distributions of the delta behaviours of AVs are hard to capture and shown in simulations. While microscopic simulations in general mimic the vehicle behaviours better than macroscopic simulations, mirroring the delta behaviours (above bullet) with preferably the embedded vehicle models from the chosen microscopic traffic simulation software VISSIM, is difficult especially in a unique edge case like UC₄. The vehicle models used to simulate the abovementioned behaviours are further discussed in the key technologies section.
- In UC₄, a sudden obstacle of a break-down vehicle is the unusual situation that causes traffic flow disturbances in one-lane two directional urban road network. Human drivers in non-AVs rely on experience, ROTRs, and negotiating with common understanding of informal rules (hand gestures and eye contact). Non-AVs can utilise the “free” opposite lane from a traffic network optimisation perspective. AVs could have difficulties finding the safe gap on the opposite lane to overtake break-down vehicle, especially when the traffic becomes heavy on the opposite lane. TM messages can provide situational awareness outside the perception of AVs. AV-without-trust could show hesitancy, stopping for an extended period until backup system intervenes.

Risk:

- Based in the first cycle, UC₄ might not be able to identify the deviating behaviours of AVs in comparison to non-AVs from the other use cases due to the parallel on-going work and the network approach of UC₄.
- Programming of the varied responses and interactions among non-AVs, AV-with-trust, AV-without-trust could pose unanticipated risks of network-wide unexpected vehicle behaviours disturbances, which might require revision of the UC₄ design in the second cycle of AITHENA.
- Microsimulations of a large-scale network with customized script for vehicle behaviours and communication require significant computational resources and sophisticated modelling techniques. To have statistically significant results from traffic simulations, multiple runs of each seed and different seeds are used. Possible risks here could be inefficient simulation tool performance and computational cost.

4.4.2. Solution

Functional description

When considering AVs and edge cases, integrating AVs into traffic systems can impact the traffic dynamics on the network level. Edge cases can disrupt traffic flow if not supported by mitigating traffic management measures. As a concept, AITHENA will consider a hierarchical traffic management approach with control actions at different levels to support AVs in the edge case scenarios.

At the top level, a centralized Traffic Management System (TMS) sets overall strategy and measures. The second level involves road infrastructure linking vehicles and the TMS by collecting data through sensors, cameras, and probe vehicle data such as floating car data (FCD), and relaying TMS decisions through variable message signs, traffic lights, and V2X. The third level is the vehicles, which also send and receive information about the status of traffic and ODDs. Vehicles are categorized as non-AVs, AV-with-trust, AV-without-trust and standard vehicle classification types such as Light Goods Vehicles (LGV) and Heavy Goods Vehicles (HGV) (fixed to 5% and 2% respectively in the first cycle).

AV-with-trust trusts outside information sources, such as the TMS and can use that information to overcome certain situations (i.e., edge cases) while still showing the driving characteristics of an automated vehicle. AV-without-trust does not trust outside information sources will struggle to overcome the said situations and will either proceed less efficiently or possibly less safe and/or need support from a backup system (e.g., fallback driver, remote supervision system, etc.) to find a solution. Besides these specific behaviours, the driving characteristics are determined by the simulation software vehicle models which are explained in the next section.

The identified edge cases form the other AITHENA use cases, and possibly edge cases from other sources, can be used in several scenarios. In addition, using traffic management concepts, these scenario measures can be conceptualised to mitigate the deviating behaviours of AVs in those edge cases. For the evaluation of the traffic dynamics, it is not necessary to fully implement the traffic

management actors and information flow. However, the effect thereof needs to be mirrored in the simulation. It is important that the specific sequence of events and required behaviours are orchestrated in the scenario to be able to assess them. To that end the microsimulation software will be connected to custom programming. The custom programming allows directly interfacing with any actor or network feature in the simulation at any given time. That way, the impact of conceptualised traffic management measures can be implemented in the simulation, and it is ensured that the scenario unfolds as intended to reflect the identified edge case.

During the running of the simulations while the scenarios unfold, the behaviours of all vehicles and other relevant are logged. Using those logs, the travel times, following distance, traffic volumes, etc. are calculated which serve as input for the efficiency, safety, and sustainability KPIs.

This will be done multiple times with varying vehicle mixes (i.e., ratios of non-AV, AV-with-trust, AV-without-trust, LGV, and HGV) and different levels of service (LOS) (Transportation Research Board 2010). That way, KPIs can be calculated for many different traffic situations. Combining the KPI results with the scenarios and vehicle mixes, an overview is created which shows which impact AVs can have on the network level traffic dynamics given that combination. This will show what benefit outside information and the trust therein can provide. In addition, knowing the impact, prevents unexpected changes in traffic dynamics thereby increasing the trust in AVs in general.

Key technologies/AI-based models

In the first AITHEA cycle, several key technologies are applied in use case 4:

1. The simulation network is an encapsulated urban network with three consecutive signalised intersections running real life traffic data sets and optimised signal controls, see Figure 30.

One of the key technologies applied in use case 4 is the base urban traffic situation of simulation network, which is a complete representation of the real-life site in operation at the Dutch municipality Heemstede with a cut of intensive traffic area (Dutch municipality project: Oversteek Adriaan Pauwlaan - Herenweg). The simulation network of use case 4 was chosen to study the explainability, interpretability and trust of AVs, and the interactions with non-AVs, other road users and infrastructure.

2. The non-AV behaviours are simulated with the default driving behaviour parameters in VISSIM, which is chosen due to the ability of simulating complex network with different features to model AVs, non-AVs behaviours and their interactions with each other and with other road users in the current operational domain.

PTV VISSIM 2024 comes with its set of cars following models: Wiedemann 74 and Wiedemann 99, in addition to the option of customizable behaviours. The Wiedemann 99 model is chosen to simulate the non-AVs in use case 4 because on the one hand, such a model can simulate the heterogeneous behaviour of diverse drivers. On the other hand, the car following behaviours of AVs in VISSIM are based on the Wiedemann 99 model.

The default attribute values of the Wiedemann 99 model: CCo to CC9 are implemented to non-AV to simulate the reference model of desired good behaviours. The complete list of attribute values is provided in D3.2. The AV behaviours are comparable to each parameter (CCo to CC9), see Table 5.

Table 5: Comparison of parameters between AV cautious and non-AV in VISSIM 2024.

	Model	Parameters	AV driving logic	non-AV
			cautious	default
Following behaviours	Wiedermann 99	CC0	default	default
		CC1	higher	default
		CC2	smaller	default
		CC3	higher	default
		CC4	smaller	default
		CC5	smaller	default
		CC6	default	default
		CC7	smaller	default
		CC8	default	default
		CC9	default	default

3. The AV behaviours are simulated in VISSIM by applying the extended features based on the AV driving logic studied in CoEXist project, a European Union’s Horizon 2020 funded project (Sukennik & Kautzsch 2018).

In AITHEA, it is assumed that under certain circumstances, especially under edge cases, the AVs react and behave differently comparing to human-driven vehicles due to Automated Driving System (ADS) controlled by its AI algorithms, and due to various AI logics and learning algorithms of various AV models. The introduction of AVs from 0% to 100% uptakes is expected to impact the traffic performance on the network level differently. Therefore, virtual testing in simulation setup with calibrated demonstrator configurations, is inevitable and necessary.

Based on the simulation approach of use case 4, the fundamental key technology in use case 4 is the state-of-the-art modelling of AVs and non-AVs in real-world network and calibrated traffic management datasets, simulated in a VISSIM microscopic simulation environment. The behaviours of AV and its AI-based logics are enforced by imposing an additional function with four new features rail safe, cautious, normal, and all-knowing.

Table 6: Automated vehicle driving logics in VISSIM (developed under CoEXist project)

Driving logic	Recommended setting for new features			
	Enforce absolute breaking distance	Use implicit stochastics	Number of interaction vehicles	Increased desired acceleration
rail safe	ON	OFF	1	100%
cautious	ON	OFF	1	100%
normal	OFF	OFF	1	100-110%
all-knowing	OFF	OFF	>1	110%

In CCAM, AVs is a key technology that provides mobility possibility, interacting with other road users and influencing travel experiences on the traffic network level. VISSIM new features were developed under intensive research of CoEXist, where recommended default values are researched and included in VISSIM newer versions.

In AITHENA, a two-step Sensitivity Analysis (SA) screening is applied here to the four AV driving logics. Step one of the SA screening filters out the AV rail safe feature due the deterministic behaviours, such as pre-defined path, physical lane separation, no lane change and no un-signalised intersection etc., which are suitable for closed environment instead of public urban road network. Step two of the SA performs experiments using the AV cautious, AV normal and AV all-knowing features sequentially on a simplified network. The AV cautious, AV normal and AV all-knowing met the functional requirements of vehicles and infrastructure in use case 4.

The SA experiments of these three types of AV behaviours on the simplified network with use case 4 scenario timelines, show that AV cautious is more closely related to the AV behaviours we expected in use case 4 scenarios in the first cycle. 1) the default AV cautious parameters captured the safe characteristics 2) the Rules Of The Road (ROTRs) requirements are respected by AV cautious 3) only using AV cautious reflects less diverse behavioural competency of AV, but more evidential to show the impact of AI-based mixed traffic on a network level. Therefore, the AV cautious is applied to use case 4 in the first cycle of AITHENA to perform the study on a complicated network as a start, and possibly the AV normal and AV all-knowing will be applied during the second cycle of AITHENA.

Scope and restrictions

This section introduces the scope and restrictions of UC₄. Since the key technologies applied are mostly in the setting up of UC₄ in the simulation environment, we further explained the scope, categorisation and limitation of several related variables.

The scope of UC₄ includes urban network, where UC₄ studied behaviours and interactions of AVs and non-AVs in complicated real-world urban settings with multiple intersections, communication among road actors and different traffic conditions, especially in edge cases where a vehicle breakdown incident would trigger greater delta behaviours between AVs and non-AVs.

In the first cycle, the scope of the simulation network is a single lane two directional road section. Due to the computational and calibration reasons, the size of the network will not be too large in the

second cycle either. On the one hand, the simulation of V2X message transmission and vehicle communication functionalities as well as KPIs such as bandwidth, latency, is out of UC₄ scope. On the other hand, the focus is on the behavioural of AVs and non-AVs upon successfully receiving of the I2V messages.

Based on the above traffic network and communication scope and restriction, three primary variables were categorised to examine the role of trust plays in different simulation scenarios.

- Level of Service (LOS): UC₄ configures traffic flows according to different LOS. Different traffic flow conditions were simulated to assess how congestion levels impact AVs and non-AVs vehicle behaviours.
- Percentage of AV (penetration rates): A fixed composition mix of passenger vehicles, light goods vehicles, and heavy goods vehicles is configured. The passenger vehicles on the network are configured according to the vehicle mixes matrix of AVs and non-AVs with varying penetration rates of AVs (the matrix is read by the script to perform simulations automatically).
- Percentage of trust: Percentage of trust corresponds to the percentages of AVs that adapt to the suggested action from a third party, such as traffic management centre, roadside infrastructure, remote support centre, etc.

Regarding restrictions, UC₄ is limited to driving behaviours that can be realistically mirrored and simulated within the VISSIM microsimulation software. Moreover, customised vehicle models or new advanced AI findings from other use cases are restricted in the first cycle of AITHENA.

UC₄ is restricted to plausible, everyday driving situations. Edge cases involving collisions or other extreme driving behaviours will be safeguarded within VISSIM microsimulation based on the chosen Wiedermann vehicle model to avoid unrealistic or overly dangerous situations.

Scenarios/use case story for CCAM applications

Automated vehicles are likely to stop when they encounter a sudden obstruction on their lane and there is no obvious way to circumvent the obstruction. An example is given in the figure below. There is a double solid line separating the two directions of traffic which normally one is not allowed to cross. However, in this scenario, overtaking via the opposite lane is allowed. Without support from an outside information source such as traffic management or fleet control, the AV remains stuck. The AV needs some outside guidance to overcome this situation and needs to trust that guidance. AVs that don't trust the guidance remain stuck for a certain period before a handover takes place or remote support solution solves the situation. AVs that do trust the guidance, can use that information to overtake the obstacle by crossing the double solid line when the situation allows (i.e., the opposite lane is free). On a side note: notice how the opposite traffic leaves space for the overtaking. This is a clear example of rules of the road that might be specifically challenging for AVs to adapt.

Figure 30: Lane obstruction with double solid line in the middle – Kersenbaan, Amerfoort, The Netherlands.

To evaluate the implication on the network level of such a scenario, a virtual network is created using the VISSIM simulation software. The figure below shows the network which is part of the road network of the Dutch municipality Heemstede. This network contains a part of infrastructure that entails the situation described above. Using this network a vehicle breakdown incident is simulated at location X that obstructs the single-lane northbound carriageway. Following vehicles approaching the incident from upstream must use the closest opposite lane of the 2-lane southbound carriageway to overtake the incident. Normal vehicles and AVs trusting guidance information overtake the incident when the traffic situation on the opposite lane allows. The time they remain stuck is interpreted as the time needed for a backup system to help the vehicle overtake.

Figure 31: Simulation(left) and geographic (right) network overview of use case 4 – part of Heemstede

First the traffic in the network is normal until at a certain moment an incident occurs at location X. The incident remains there to capture the effect of AVs having difficulty to overtake. Then, after a while, the incident is resolved. After a period of normalisation, traffic is back to normal. Thus, a normal period, the period during the incident, the normalisation period, and the normal period afterwards are captured when running the simulation.

In the section above (scope and restrictions), primary parameter sets used in the simulation are introduced. For the second cycle, the AV behaviour on the network level will be studied by introducing, for example, other types of situations/incidents, behaviours adapted from the other AITHENA use cases, other types of networks, and possibly other parameter sets, for example, different traffic composition, LOS, and/or percentage of trust).

4.4.3. Requirements

The simulation network of UC₄ baseline is designed and prepared to fulfil the UC₄ demonstrator pertaining to the following points:

- Real-world traffic data, evening peak hour traffic volumes
- Calibrated data set of above with 75% of the evening peak volumes to avoid gridlock
- Deployed traffic systems in operation
- Non-AVs behaviours represent the reference model of the desired good behaviours.
- AVs behaviours are benchmarked to the above reference model, focusing on edge cases.
- Non-AVs and AVs are susceptible to input from CITS/V2X sources and able to process the transmitted messages (e.g. CAM, MAP, SPAT, MCM, CPM).
- TMC monitors the whole network operation and broadcasts messages that can support the AVs and non-AVs in edge cases.

This section further elaborates the above UC₄ demonstrator regarding the following requirement aspects: functional data requirements, operational requirements, legal requirements and useability and human interaction requirements.

Functional data requirements

The functional data requirements of UC₄ covers the basic data requirements and prerequisites. UC₄ prerequisites refer to the vehicle and infrastructure side requirements functioning in the background. UC₄ directly considers the impact of functioning vehicle communication, road-side infrastructure and traffic management, while UC₄ does not simulate these prerequisites.

The basic data requirements include UC₄ environmental conditions (time-of-day and weather conditions), traffic flow, vehicle types, specifications and behaviours (including edge cases).

- UC₄ environmental conditions requirements include time-of-day and weather conditions. UC₄ chose evening peak hour traffic volume of real-world traffic data in the second cycle. While this is less relevant to be considered in the proof-of-concept network in the first cycle, the time-of-day can have impact on decision-making in the second cycle. Another requirement is the weather conditions, where no adverse weather conditions nor significant changes of weather attributes is considered.
- UC₄ traffic flow data requirements include data on the traffic incident (a sudden vehicle breakdown) and traffic flow data on all the ingress approaches. The traffic incident contains the timestamp, location, duration of the vehicle breakdown. The real-world traffic flow data refers to the historical traffic flow data of the second cycle network, which is based on vehicle counts, speeds, densities, and road actors' compositions.
- UC₄ vehicle type requirements refer to 5% Light Goods Vehicles (LGV) and 2% Heavy Goods Vehicles (HGV) as mentioned in the scope section above.
- UC₄ vehicle specifications requirements refer to background details of non-AVs and AVs. These vehicles shall reflect the sensor capabilities and limitations of AVs, regarding perception range, field of view and accuracy. UC₄ assumes vehicle specifications requirements as prerequisites without impact to the vehicle behaviours.
- UC₄ vehicle behaviours requirements refer to the non-AV behaviours (benchmarked as the reference model of the desired behaviours), and the AV behaviours.
- In UC₄, non-AVs should react to the vehicle breakdown incident based on the human driver's perception and judgment. Non-AVs should follow common sense driving logic, overtaking the vehicle breakdown incident by crossing solid lines and using opposite lane when it is safe to do so, considering the oncoming traffic and other road conditions.
- In UC₄, AVs should adhere to traffic rules but also capable of overriding certain rules (e.g., crossing a solid line) based on trusted TM messages. AVs should show adaptive car-following behaviours, adapting speed and trajectory based on real-time traffic and environmental data. AVs should be able to perceive incidents and obstacles, decide on appropriate actions (stop, wait for remote control, overtake), and execute these actions safely.

Operational / performance requirements

The operational/performance requirements of UC₄ describes the vehicle and infrastructure side requirements in the operation level of traffic network. For AVs to operate safely, efficiently and predictable on the transport system level, strategic and tactical data from traffic management systems are relevant to situational awareness, path planning and manoeuvre decision making.

- TM should support AV performance in edge cases from a network perspective.
- Vehicles should be connected and receptive to V2X message.
- V2X message formats shall be standardized.
- TM should be able to broadcast V2X to bridge the ODD deterioration gap.
- KPIs regarding performance requirements: the use case during operation in simulation environment should not cause traffic congestions especially gridlock, which make the functional validation of the TM measures not feasible.

Legal requirements

For the first cycle, there are limited legal requirements in comparison to the second cycle. The second cycle will involve communication as a domain which will include, for instance, messages for connected and automated vehicles or other kinds, to inform other vehicles of the presence of an AV vehicle. This will involve addressing GDPR guidelines to provide information relating to the identity of the vehicle.

Useability and human interaction requirements

In the rationale section, UC₄ mentioned that on a network level, the introduction of AVs with potentially different driving behaviours may influence the driving characteristics of non-AVs. This section discusses the useability and human interaction requirements of UC₄.

- From a mobility perspective, there are several human elements from diverse stakeholders such as citizens, traffic participants, city authorities etc. Traffic management at transport and policy level should consider the perspectives and interactions of various stakeholders. Moreover, the transparency of AI based AV technology is also paramount to increase public acceptance and trust in AVs, especially in edge cases.
- The response of non-AVs to AVs with deviating behaviours will have implications on the driving characteristics of non-AVs. Human drivers in non-AV should be able to respond effectively to AVs that exhibit deviating behaviours. Non-AVs should understand and anticipate AV actions, such as unexpected longer stops and waiting time due to sudden obstacles and latency in vehicle communications.
- Interaction of the AI models within AVs, in-vehicle fallback-ready user, and remote driving system should be reliable. The AI models within AVs, as well as remote driving systems, should be reliable and capable of seamless interaction with in-vehicle fallback-ready user. This ensures that in edge cases, the transition among AI control and human user or remote intervention is smooth and safe. In addition, the protocols for remote intervention should be well-defined and tested in edge cases, to ensure that when AVs require assistance from a remote driving system, the transition is with minimum latency and does not cause delays or safety risks.

5. CONCLUSION

This chapter wraps up by contemplating the key findings from the survey results, which highlight user viewpoints on Autonomous Vehicles (AVs) and AI-driven CCAM technology that are further incorporated into the use case definition, where it examines how the use case caters to user needs, expectations, and concerns, providing a concise summary.

5.1. Reflection towards user requirements for AITHENA Use cases

5.1.1. UC1: Trustworthy perception systems for CCAM

The solutions developed within the use case focus on target user groups such as users, developers, researchers, and regulatory authorities. These are especially applicable to the urban environment scenarios involving streets, city centres and residential areas, and involve any form of automated mobility as a mode (e.g., cars, personal transport, robo-taxis, shuttle).

Table 7: UC1 summarized based on scope, demonstrator, primary objective and scenario

Scope	
Target user groups	System users, developers, researchers, certification authorities and regulatory authorities.
Geographic boundary	Urban environment
Modes of transport	Any form of automated mobility as a mode
Primary objective	To facilitate the utilisation of a pedestrian detection system in a use case demonstrator. This aims to enhance safety measures, especially in scenarios where pedestrian detection lies within the safety-critical path.
Demonstrator	The pedestrian detection system is tested in an offline demonstrator using recorded data from several datasets and derived through simulation. In Phase II, the system will be integrated in a real-world demonstrator-vehicle (car or automated shuttle) showcasing the UC results.
Scenario example	An urban scenario is considered where an obstacle blocks the view on a pedestrian. The solutions developed under the use case focuses on conflict resolution by the perception system.

Considering the user mobility needs, the use case has the potential to contribute towards building high level of trust for the end-users in AVs in rural/suburban areas (as the survey results showed low/moderate level of trust in self-driving vehicles in rural and suburban environments) unless the implementation approaches in the future accept AVs as a predominantly urban technology. Regarding suburban and interurban environment, as the objective of the UC is to facilitate utilisation of a pedestrian detection system, scenarios including highways are not addressed through this use case as pedestrians are less frequent on highways.

Focusing on the user expectations, the use case tries to demonstrate robust perception (mainly focusing on the pedestrians) also in adverse weather conditions, which influences the type of information the self-driving vehicle’s sensors will recognise. This is mainly relevant considering the occupants/passengers in an AV, where user’s access to information via vehicle’s sensors is important. Based on the situations where conflicting perceptions occur, the perception system within the use case will inform the user or the onboard/remote supervisor to take over the control of the vehicle (termed as extremely important information to have by the survey respondents). The use case addresses the information on what the vehicle perceives and acknowledges through which sensor and at what confidence level the detection system is on.

Based on the concerns reflected in the survey results, the use case investigates the robustness of perception in adverse conditions additionally giving a measure of confidence in the detection. The issues regarding privacy concerns are to be addressed through data cards, while the ethical bias based on appearance will be dealt through the combination of model cards and data cards (making sure that there is no discrimination towards AV users based on their appearance). Through reliable pedestrian detection system on a long-term basis, the trust levels of cyclists and pedestrians towards AVs will be influenced and it will have a positive impact indirectly. With the equipment or system failure reflected as one of the main factors discouraging self-driving cars in the survey, the use case will address potential sensor failure as one of the scenarios within the AITHENA project timeline.

5.1.2. UC2: AI-extended situational awareness / understanding

UC2.1 Collision prediction with hybrid AI data fusion

The solutions developed within the use case focus on target user groups such as system users (i.e., end users), development engineers, auto-makers and researchers. The geographical scope of the use case includes both urban (e.g., road crossing) and non-urban environments (i.e. rural/suburban areas) involving AVs as a mode of transport. The urban scenarios include interactions between pedestrians and vehicles, especially those related to potentially risky situations, such as zebra-crossing situations, pedestrians partially occluded by parked cars, etc. The non-urban scenarios include interaction between vehicles (i.e. cut-in/cut-out scenario, hard brake, etc.)

Table 8: UC2.1 summarized based on scope, demonstrator, primary objective and scenario

Scope	
Target user groups	System users, development engineers, auto-makers and researchers.
Geographic boundary	Urban, rural and suburban environment
Modes of transport	Any form of automated mobility as a mode
Primary objective	To produce a SLS, using graphical database technologies and a set of rules that detect edge cases and create rich explanations of the scene.
Demonstrator	Semantic labelling is applied offline (in the 1st cycle) to create queries to identify situations of interest (e.g., near collision). Real-time implementation (in the 2nd cycle) will explore prediction capabilities of collision and other situations.
Scenario example	Urban scenario: Interaction between pedestrians and vehicles (e.g., zebra crossing)

Non-urban scenario: Interaction between vehicles (e.g., overtaking, over speeding, near miss collision)

Considering the user mobility needs, the objective of the use case is to assist in the identification of edge-cases for the evaluation which will increase the ability of the developers and auto-makers for testing rural/suburban, inter-city and urban scenarios. This will in turn contribute towards higher level of trust in AVs, especially in rural/suburban areas which currently from the survey results reflect low level of trust from people.

Addressing the user expectations towards AVs and AI-based CCAM applications, the use case will facilitate the testing of edge-scenarios which enhances the ability of automakers to push safety features that may reduce the amount of vehicle accidents (which supports the expectations derived from the user survey reflecting strong agreement with fewer vehicle crashes). The use case, to some extent, will also impact the decision-making system through scene understanding of the edge-case scenarios. This will contribute to the information access the end-user (e.g., occupant, passenger in an AV) will have based on how the AV makes its decision.

Reflecting upon the user concerns towards self-driving vehicles, the use case will build trust towards AVs to be safe and reliant during extreme weather conditions, build trust towards user comfort in AVs interacting with human-driven vehicles, and contribute towards building confidence for vulnerable road users (pedestrians/cyclists) in using shared road space with AVs. This will be done through sufficient testing on edge-cases which may include extreme weather conditions, human-driven vehicles, and pedestrians and/or cyclists in shared road space.

UC2.2 Robust prediction modules for robo-taxis in urban environment

The solutions developed within the use case focus on target user groups involving system users (i.e. the end users), developers, and researchers. In contrast to UC2.1, the geographical scope of the use will primarily focus on urban environments (such as segments of road infrastructure with surrounding objects, for example, buildings) involving cars (i.e., robo-taxi).

Table 9: UC2.2 summarized based on scope, demonstrator, primary objective and scenario

Scope	
Target user groups	System users, developers, and researchers.
Geographic boundary	Urban environment
Modes of transport	Cars (e.g., robo-taxi)
Primary objective	To develop a trustworthy prediction module providing a robo-taxi with precise information on the motion of observed traffic participants (including design of module predicting long-term motion and uncertainty considerations).
Demonstrator	In the 1st cycle the individual parts of this demonstrator has been developed. In the 2nd cycle the parts will be combined to a holistic demonstrator. The overall demonstration will be done virtually.
Scenario example	Urban scenarios in which each traffic participant is simultaneously subjected to different types of interactions such as single and multi-lane urban intersection

scenarios involving trucks, cars, motorbikes, cyclists, and pedestrians as traffic participants.

Based on the user mobility needs involving different activities, the use case through the development of robo-taxis provides an alternative for passenger transportation supporting any activity (e.g., groceries, sports) the passengers do at their destination and is not linked directly to any specific activity. The use case will have an impact on the user mobility needs which may include shorter travel time that traditional taxis cannot guarantee. With the robo-taxi being an automated transport vehicle, it is possible that its application could promote and contribute towards the scenario of using automated public transport making them more accepted in the public sphere (considering majority of survey respondents were extremely/very interested in the scenario of using automated public transport with fixed routes and high frequency). With the environment of robo-taxi's use being urban its continuous use in urban environments would, with time, contribute to a higher level of trust in AVs.

It is expected that the robo-taxi's interaction with its passengers will include displaying the crucial environmental information that impacts the robo-taxi's decision-making process. The use case will not focus on the scenario directly where the occupant (i.e. the passenger) will be able to take over the control of the AV. However, robo-taxi might still require the presence of a human driver that could take this role if necessary. Considering notifying other road users including pedestrians or cyclists of the presence of the AV, the robo-taxi should provide a form of signalling to the surrounding traffic participants.

Lastly, based on the concerns reflected through the survey, ensuring safety of both primary and secondary i.e., the passengers and the surrounding traffic participants, only leads to the acceptance of the robo-taxis as a transport alternative. Addressing this concern towards safety is one of the main purposes for this UC. The robo-taxi will be used in an urban environment that is expected to include both human-driven and partially or fully automated vehicles. Proof of their safe use in such an environment will promote greater trust in their use. Whether it is through redundant safety mechanisms or the presence of human drivers, the use of robo-taxis must address failure scenarios (which was reflected strongly in the survey as factors discouraging use of AVs) before they can be seen in use in urban environments.

5.1.3. UC3: Trustworthy and human-understandable decision making

The solutions developed within the use case focus on target user groups involving occupants of the AVs, developers, testers and regulatory authorities. The geographical scope of the use will primarily focus on urban environments involving any form of automated mobility as a mode such as cars, personal transport, robo-taxis, etc.

Table 10: UC3 summarized based on scope, demonstrator, primary objective and scenario

Scope	
Target user groups	AV occupants, developers, testers and regulatory authorities.
Geographic boundary	Urban environment
Modes of transport	Any form of automated mobility
Primary objective	To showcase a robust system for vehicle guidance alongside the explanation of decisions to the user of the system before, while, or after they have been

executed (involving integration of XAI interface into algorithms for decision-making and increasing robustness of vehicle guidance system).

Demonstrator The vehicle guidance system is implemented in a digital twin of an automated vehicle and its environment using simulation tools. During Phase II, the system will be integrated in a real-world demonstrator-vehicle (car or automated shuttle) showcasing the UC results.

Scenario example Urban scenario involving the decision-making system explaining the AV occupant of non-intuitive braking due to occluded vehicle.

Based on the mobility needs reflected through the user survey, the use case will contribute towards building trust in AVs within the urban environment, where the results and methodologies applied can be transferred to other geographical areas that are not focused or demonstrated in this use case. The use case builds trust towards AVs as the main objective is to demonstrate robust and trustworthy decision making and corresponding vehicle guidance in urban environments. The solutions developed will have a direct impact on the personal safety and predictability of the vehicle behaviour.

The solutions demonstrated by the UC will have direct impact on AV's decision-making and will provide information to the end-user. This is done via prototypical implementation of visualization concepts that explain non-intuitive behaviour of the vehicle. In situations with low competence indication for the implemented planning-stack, the system might inform the user / (onboard/remote) supervisor to take over the control of the vehicle. In combination with the traffic management in UC₄, the expected impact will be on a lower travel time for the vehicle. In addition, the task of vehicle guidance is usually under the objective of safety, efficiency and comfort. Next to this the UC also addresses the comfort of the occupant w.r.t. provided information especially in situations that are not predictable for the occupant e.g. where the vehicle does not behave like expected. Therefore, the guidance system can provide information relating to route the vehicle takes, trip duration, traffic conditions, and what the AV perceives along the way since its decision usually builds up on these.

Focusing on the user concerns, the use case will build trust towards user comfort in AVs interacting with human-driven vehicles (which is also reflected through the survey results, with majority of the user groups involving pedestrians, decision makers, developers and especially AV users reflect positive perspective on the aspect). Especially in mixed traffic (AV and human-driven vehicles), unforeseen situations may occur, which this use case tries to address to. For instance, this is addressed in the scenario involving robustness of hybrid AI planning stack against unknown contexts. Robust and understandable behaviour of the vehicle impacts positively to foster trust of occupants regarding their personal safety. Even in unforeseen situations, the users are informed why the vehicle takes certain decision which also builds trust in situations when the vehicle behaviour was not what the occupant expected.

5.1.4. UC₄: AI-based traffic management

The solutions developed within the use case focus on target user groups involving road authorities, road operators/managers, fleet operators, road users (i.e. AV in-vehicle/remote operators, non-AV on-vehicle drivers). The geographical scope of the use case will primarily focus on urban networks (representation of real-life site in Dutch municipality) involving both AVs and non-AVs as the mode of transport. In contrast to other use cases in AITHENA, this use case focuses on a network rather than

single or a few vehicles because the impact can be minor for single vehicle and more substantial due to the cumulative effect of a small deviation in the behaviour of multiple vehicles.

Table 11: UC4 summarized based on scope, demonstrator, primary objective and scenario

Scope	
Target user groups	AV/non-AV drivers, AV in-vehicle/remote operators, fleet operators, road operators and authorities.
Geographic boundary	Urban environment
Modes of transport	AVs and Non-AVs.
Primary objective	To understand the causality between the AI behaviour of AVs and the network performance in terms of efficiency, safety, and sustainability. This involves analysing the response of AI-models to traffic management data, at strategic, tactical, and operational levels.
Demonstrator	It is a macroscopic microsimulation where the behaviours of AVs are simulated in a traffic network to assess the impact of those behaviours on the network level. A demonstrator can entail different networks and/or AV behaviours.
Scenario example	The AI-Based traffic management scenario is simulated with microscopic traffic simulation software VISSIM on the urban road network in Heemstede, the Netherlands.

Focusing on the user mobility needs, the use case will have an indirect impact on how people choose their mode of transport for different activities. One example is logistics using AVs, where the traffic management will facilitate the network optimisation where these AV's uptakes and trips are increasing. Considering the use case's demonstrator focuses on the urban environment, it might have an extended minor impact to contribute towards higher level of trust in AVs in rural and suburban environment (with desk study of highway-specific safety protocols, dedicated AV lanes, and guidelines) by helping the AVs to integrate with traditional traffic systems and infrastructure, data sharing and real-time Information and incident management. With the level of interest in using an automated public transport being high amongst the survey respondents, analysing the impact of edge cases for certain AVs can raise the need for dedicated infrastructure (i.e. lanes) and digital infrastructure to support automated public transport. Also, the routes might be designed in such a way to avoid certain edge cases deteriorating the Operational Design Domain (ODD) of the AVs.

The use case will influence the type of information the vehicle sensors recognise and will provide information to the AVs which are not clear to be detected in edge cases. This will impact the AVs and non-AV's decision making by providing real-time information. UC₄ will mainly focus on edge/corner cases where in the complex urban situations the occupants will have to take over control (this was termed as extremely important information to have access to by the survey respondents). The use case will facilitate the end users and optimise the network performance with providing information. Regarding the first cycle, the use case will not take into consideration the presence of onboard/remote supervision for the AVs. In addition, the use case will not directly impact the information flow to the pedestrians/cyclist over the presence of AVs in their proximity. The use case will focus on user requirements for a comfortable travel in the AV by providing traffic management information about incidents, road works, rerouting, making it possible to inform the user about certain decisions made

by the AV. Considering user expectations towards situations such as less congestion, fewer vehicle crashes, fewer vehicles on road, and mobility system being more sustainable, UC₄ will have an indirect impact. Supporting AVs with TM information via digital infrastructure can increase the reliability and robustness which results in less congestion and less travel time. Assessing edge cases and knowing parts of the network makes it possible to plan to avoid those parts.

Based on the identified concerns from the user survey, the use case does not refer to extreme weather conditions and building confidence of AV users towards privacy protection (with cybersecurity not being within the scope). It will play an indirect role in building trust towards user comfort in AVs interacting with human-driven vehicles by providing and sharing data to increase transparency. With the use case focusing more on a network level than a vehicle level, on the one hand, it does not consider individual usage of AVs, and does not contribute towards building trust through no discrimination for the users based on their appearance. On the other hand, in the second cycle of the AITHENA project, UC₄ will provide insight into how introducing AVs will impact the safety on the network level and build trust towards AVs to be safe during travel by assessing safety measures/indicators as input for KPIs. It will address scenarios including equipment/system failure of an AV (identified as the most critical factor discouraging use of AVs) by assessing the impact of AVs not being able to continue. Perhaps this will not specifically involve breakdowns, but certainly include situations where AVs are reaching the limit of its capabilities or ODD.

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ANNEX I

This annexure shows the published user survey template including survey logic, which was finalised based on the workshops mentioned in chapter 2 as follows:

Start of Block: Intro

Thank you for taking the time to reply to this survey on self-driving vehicles, which is part of the EU AITHENA project. It should take 10-15 minutes to complete.

This survey aims to understand people's needs, expectations, and concerns in relation to all types of road-based passenger vehicles (buses, taxis, shared vehicles, personal vehicles, etc.) which are fully automated and self-driving. For the purposes of this survey, self-driving vehicles are vehicles:

- in which the occupants of the vehicle do not participate in driving activities but must be prepared to take over control if requested by the vehicle for safety,
- which communicate on an ongoing basis with other vehicles on the road and with their surroundings (e.g. with traffic lights),
- obey all traffic regulations (including speed limits).

Data protection: This survey does not collect any personal details from respondents and all information is fully anonymised. For more information on the project's privacy policy please visit: <https://aithena.eu/privacy-policy/>

End of Block: Intro

Start of Block: Profile

Q2.2 How do you describe yourself?

- Male (1)
- Female (2)
- Non-binary (3)
- Prefer to self-describe (4) _____
- Prefer not to say (5)

Q2.3 How old are you?

- Under 18 (1)
- 18-30 years old (2)
- 31-40 years old (3)
- 41-50 years old (4)
- 51-60 years old (5)
- 61-70 years old (6)
- 70+ years old (7)
- Prefer not to say (8)

Skip To: End of Survey If How old are you? = Under 18

Q2.4 What is the highest level of education you have completed?

- Primary school (1)
- Secondary / technical / vocational education (2)
- Bachelor degree (3)
- Masters degree (4)
- PhD / post-graduate studies (5)
- Other (6)
- Prefer not to say (7)

Q2.5 What is your personal annual income before taxes?

- Less than €10,000 (1)
- €10,000 - €24,999 (2)
- €25,000 - €39,999 (3)
- €40,000 - €59,999 (4)
- €60,000 - €79,999 (7)
- €80,000 - €99,999 (8)
- €100,000 - €199,999 (9)
- More than €200,000 (5)
- Prefer not to say (6)

Q2.6 In which country do you currently reside?

▼ Afghanistan (1) ... Zimbabwe (1357)

Q2.7 How would you describe your place of residence?

- Urban (1)
- Suburban (2)
- Rural (3)

Q2.8 Do you have a driver's license?

- Yes (1)
- No (2)

Q2.9 Do you own a car or do you have access to a car (either privately owned or car sharing)?

- Yes (1)
- No (2)

Q2.10 What is your knowledge about self-driving vehicles?

- No knowledge/never heard of it (1)
- I've heard about it but don't know exactly what it is (2)
- I have some understanding of it (3)
- I understand the concept quite well (4)
- I understand the concept well enough to explain it to others (5)

Q2.11 Have you ever ridden in a self-driving vehicle?

- Yes (1)
- Not completely self driving but in a vehicle with some automated features (6)
- No (2)

Q2.12 What relationship do you have (or do you envision having) with self-driving vehicles? (*choose all that apply*)

- I'm a developer of self-driving vehicle technologies or services (1)
- I'm a decision maker or planner involved in decisions as to whether self-driving vehicles will be allowed and under what conditions (2)
- I use (or plan to use) a self-driving car (3)
- I am (or plan to be) a passenger in a self-driving shuttle or bus (4)
- I do not plan to travel in self-driving vehicles but am (or will be) a pedestrian or cyclist who shares the street with self-driving vehicles (5)

Display This Question:

If What relationship do you have (or do you envision having) with self-driving vehicles? (choose all... = I'm a developer of self-driving vehicle technologies or services

Or What relationship do you have (or do you envision having) with self-driving vehicles? (choose all... = I'm a decision maker or planner involved in decisions as to whether self-driving vehicles will be allowed and under what conditions

Q2.13 What is your specific role or involvement with self-driving vehicles?

- Member of the mobility department of a public authority (1)
- Member of a private organisation that develops CCAM functions (2)
- Academic, researcher, or independent expert (3)
- Public sector policy or decision maker (4)
- Other (5) _____

End of Block: Profile

Start of Block: Identification of mobility needs

Q3.1 *The following section aims to understand your mobility needs and preferences regarding self-driving vehicles.*

Again, for the purpose of this survey, self-driving vehicles are vehicles:

- in which the occupants of the vehicle do not participate in driving activities but must be prepared to take over control if requested by the vehicle for safety,
- which communicate on an ongoing basis with other vehicles on the road and with their surroundings (e.g. with traffic lights), and
- obey all traffic regulations (including speed limits).

Q3.2 What travel modes do you use most frequently for the following activities (if you generally use more than one mode on the same trip, select all modes used):

	Walk (1)	Bike (2)	Public transport (3)	Car (driver) (4)	Car (passenger) (5)	Scooter / e-scooter (6)	Other (7)	Not applicable (8)
Regular door-to-door commute (to school/work/other) (1)	<input type="checkbox"/>							
First/last mile of a journey (e.g. to reach a public transport stop/station or airport) (2)	<input type="checkbox"/>							
Journeys to accompany others (e.g. children to school) (6)	<input type="checkbox"/>							
Errands (shopping, etc.) (3)	<input type="checkbox"/>							
Leisure activities (sports, restaurants, etc.) (4)	<input type="checkbox"/>							
Going on holiday (5)	<input type="checkbox"/>							

Q3.5 How important is each of the following criteria to you when you choose your transport mode for daily trips?

Q3.3 How often would you travel in a self-driving vehicle for the following activities?

Q3.4 To what extent would you trust self-driving vehicles in each of the following environments?

Q3.6 How interested are you in using a self-driving vehicle in the following scenarios?

	Not at all interested	Slightly interested	Moderately Interested	Very Interested	Extremely Interested
	1	2	3	4	5
Owning my own. I would be responsible for finding a place to store it (similar to personal car ownership). ()					
Having access to a fleet of different kinds of shared self-driving vehicles whenever I want, booking and paying by time and distance travelled. The vehicle would pick me up at the reserved time and I am responsible for storing the vehicle only during reserved time (similar to today's car sharing). ()					
Hiring one on a pay-per-use basis to pick me up and take me where I need to go (similar to a taxi service). ()					
Booking a self-driving shuttle service that picks me up on short notice, is shared with other passengers going in a similar direction, and drops me off near my destination (similar to on-demand shuttle). ()					
Using an automated public transport vehicle (e.g. bus, shuttle) with fixed routes and stops, in a high-frequency 24hr service ()					

End of Block: Identification of mobility needs

Start of Block: Expectations

Now we would like to learn about your expectations from self-driving vehicles, including how you imagine such services will work, how you would interact with the vehicles and what impacts this could have on your daily life.

Q4.3 Where self-driving vehicles operate regularly in traffic and you are an **occupant of the self-driving vehicle**, how important do you think it is to be informed about the following:

	Not at all important	Slightly Important	Moderately Important	Very Important	Extremely Important	Not Applicable
	1	2	3	4	5	
What types of information the vehicle's sensors recognise (e.g. weather conditions, people) ()						
How the vehicle makes its decisions (e.g. to stop, give priority to others) ()						
In what situations you, as the occupant, might need to take over control ()						

Q61 Where self-driving vehicles operate regularly in traffic and you are a **passenger in a self-driving shuttle/bus**, how important do you think it is to be informed about the following:

Not at all important Slightly important Moderately important Very important Extremely important Not applicable

1 2 3 4 5

What types of information the vehicle's sensors recognise (e.g. weather conditions, people) ()	
How the vehicle makes its decisions (e.g., to stop, give priority to others) ()	
Whether there is an onboard security supervisor / backup driver ()	
Whether there is remote security supervision ()	

Q62 Where self-driving vehicles operate regularly in traffic and you are a **pedestrian or cyclist**, how important do you think it is to be informed about the following:

Not at all important Slightly important Moderately important Very important Extremely important Not applicable

1 2 3 4 5

When a self-driving vehicle is nearby ()	
How nearby self-driving vehicles make their decisions (e.g., to stop, give priority to others) ()	
When a human driver is taking control of a nearby self-driving vehicle ()	

Q4.6 How important is it for you to be able to do work or recreational activities in a self-driving vehicle?

- Not at all important (1)
- Slightly important (2)
- Moderately important (3)
- Very important (4)
- Extremely important (5)

Display This Question:

If How important is it for you to be able to do work or recreational activities in a self-driving ve... != Not at all important

Q4.7 Which activities would you like to do in a self-driving vehicle? (choose all that apply)

- Sleep (1)
- Read (documents, news, books) (2)
- Watch a video (TV, movie, series, etc.) (3)
- Use social media apps (5)
- Engage in conversation (phone, with other passengers) (7)
- Work on a computer or tablet (8)
- Other (6) _____

Display This Question:

If How important is it for you to be able to do work or recreational activities in a self-driving ve... != Not at all important

Q4.8 What would you need from the self-driving system to be comfortable doing the selected activities? (choose all that apply)

- What route the vehicle is taking to the destination (2)
- How long it will take to get there (3)
- What the traffic conditions are along the way (4)
- Information about what the vehicle is perceiving along the way (6)
- Explanations of the decisions the vehicle is making along the way (5)
- Nothing, I already feel comfortable (1)

Q4.9 Imagine a mobility system made up entirely of self-driving vehicles (personal, shared, on-demand shuttles, and regular buses) that communicate with the surrounding infrastructure (e.g. traffic signals) and coordinate actions such as which route to take, appropriate speed, and general movement. This system could be designed for safety, traffic efficiency, reduced greenhouse gas emissions, vehicle speed, passenger comfort, or other system-wide objectives.

Compared to today's mobility system with human-driven vehicles, to what extent do you agree with the following statements?

	Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree
	1	2	3	4	5
I would expect my trips to take less time ()					
I would expect to have the same amount of control over the route I travel ()					
I would expect less traffic congestion ()					
I would expect this system to be more environmentally sustainable ()					
I would expect fewer vehicles on the road ()					
I would expect fewer vehicle crashes ()					
I would expect to be able to switch to manual driving mode whenever I want (in a personal vehicle) ()					
I would expect to be able to access locations that I cannot access without self-driving vehicles ()					

Q4.11 Would you expect the vehicle to require certification by official organisations or standards? (*choose all that apply*)

- by the government (vehicle authority) - by country/state (1)
- by the government - overarching, e.g., the EU (2)
- by an organisation representing the automotive industry (3)
- by independent standards organisations (4)
- No, I would not expect certification to be required (5)

End of Block: Expectations

Start of Block: Concerns

Finally, we would like to understand your concerns with regard to self-driving vehicles.

Assume that self-driving vehicles are widely available (e.g. personal car, shared mobility like buses or taxis). You can encounter them as an occupant / passenger, pedestrian, cyclist, etc.

Q5.3 Do you agree with the following statements?

	Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree	I don't know
	1	2	3	4	5	
I would trust a self-driving vehicle to safely take me to my destination ()						
I would feel comfortable allowing my school-aged child to travel alone in a self-driving vehicle ()						
I would trust the self-driving vehicle to be safe and reliable in extreme conditions (rain, fog, snow, darkness) ()						
I would feel comfortable as an occupant without control in a self-driving vehicle ()						
I feel confident that my privacy would be protected when I use a self-driving vehicle ()						
I feel confident that I would be protected from cybersecurity breaches or data theft in a self-driving vehicle ()						
As a pedestrian or cyclist, I would feel comfortable sharing the road with self-driving vehicles ()						
I would feel comfortable about a self-driving vehicle making critical decisions where harm to humans is unavoidable ()						
I would feel comfortable with the ability of self-driving vehicles to interact with human-driven vehicles ()						
I feel confident that self-driving vehicles would behave consistently towards all people regardless of appearance (e.g. clothing, race, gender, etc.) ()						
I feel confident that I would not be wrongly held liable for a decision made by a self-driving car in which I am an occupant ()						
I feel confident in my ability to learn how to operate a self-driving car ()						

Q5.4 What are the **three** most important factors that may discourage you from riding in a self-driving vehicle?
(please either choose 3 answers or only 1 of the last two options)

- Restriction of manual driving (1)
- Unemployment due to job replacement by self-driving vehicles (3)
- Disclosing personal data (4)
- Equipment or system failure (6)
- Legal liability for occupants in case of a crash (7)
- Interactions with human-driven vehicles (8)
- Cyberattacks against the computer systems (9)
- Learning to use a self-driving vehicle (10)
- There is no reason I would not ride in a self-driving vehicle (11)
- I prefer not to respond (12)

End of Block: Concerns

Start of Block: Thank you

Q60 Thank you for taking the time to complete this survey.

AITHENA is a European research and innovation project that aims to make the technology used in AI-based self-driving vehicles trustworthy, explainable, and accountable. You can learn more about the AITHENA project and follow the results of this survey and further research on: <https://aithena.eu/>.

The AITHENA project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement number 101076754.

End of Block: Thank you

ANNEX II

This annexure shows the survey results (in charts and tables) which is discussed in Chapter 3 for the user group needs, expectations and concerns as follows:

Figure 32: Graphs showing level of trust towards self-driving vehicles in urban, suburban, and inter-city environments

Figure 33: Level of importance for criteria towards choosing a transport mode for daily trips

Typology of information and corresponding importance

Figure 34: Information vs corresponding importance for pedestrians or cyclists

Considering the Ordinal Logistic Regression (OLR) analysis for the AITHENA surveys, as they are executed in the IBM SPSS software, the reference dependent variable is ordered in a way which has a high response rate. This is part of the data cleaning and ordering it prior to any analysis. The data sample for the last category of the dependent variables is selected to be high enough to be significant. Considering there are around 340 responses, having low responses in the last category (e.g. 10) and using it as a reference category would result in non-significant values.

Considering interests from the use cases, certain pairs of dependent and independent variables were analysed through OLR. For instance, considering the relationship between dependent variable of interest in owning a personal self-driving vehicle and independent variable of income there was a significant relationship identified. The analysis reflected how **respondents having a low level of income (i.e. < 10,000€) had least interest in owning a personal AV** (with sig. <0.05 and negative estimate of 1.238). In addition, **respondents owning or having current access to car showed high interest in owning a self-driving vehicle** (with sig. <0.05 and positive estimate of 1.059).

Similarly, addressing the relationship between dependent variable of using AVs like today's car sharing scenario and independent variable representing user groups involving pedestrian and cyclists, significant relationship was identified. The user group was slightly / not interested in using self-driving car sharing services in the future (with sig.<0.05 and negative estimate of 1.225). Regarding travelling in an AV for door-to-door commute, respondents falling within the age group of 41-50 years of age preferred traveling rarely (i.e. yearly) or never for the activity in the vehicle (with sig. <0.05 and negative estimate of 1.537). The view was similar for persons with a Masters degree (with sig. <0.05 and negative estimate of 1.807). **For persons having access to cars or who owned a car, using a self-driving car daily or weekly for door-to-door commute was of high interest** (with sig. <0.05 and positive estimate of 1.454).

Case Processing Summary

		N	Marginal Percentage
How interested are you in using a self-driving vehicle in the following scenarios? - Having access to a fleet of different kinds of shared self-driving vehicles whenever I want, booking and paying by time and distance travelled. The vehicle would pick me up at the reserved time and I am responsible for storing the vehicle only during reserved time (similar to today's car sharing).	Not at all interested	54	15.9%
	Slightly interested	81	23.8%
	Moderately interested	88	25.9%
	Very interested	78	22.9%
	Extremely interested	39	11.5%
How do you describe yourself? - Selected Choice	Prefer not to say	3	0.9%
	Prefer to self-describe	1	0.3%
	Non-binary	2	0.6%
	Female	136	40.0%
	Male	198	58.2%
How old are you?	Prefer not to say	1	0.3%
	70+ years old	2	0.6%
	61-70 years old	14	4.1%
	51-60 years old	46	13.5%
	41-50 years old	64	18.8%
	31-40 years old	107	31.5%
	18-30 years old	106	31.2%
	Other	2	0.6%
What is the highest level of education you have completed?	Prefer not to say	2	0.6%
	Other	9	2.6%
	Primary school	1	0.3%
	Secondary / technical / vocational education	21	6.2%
	Bachelor degree	73	21.5%
	Masters degree	179	52.6%
	PhD / post-graduate studies	55	16.2%
What is your personal annual income before taxes?	Prefer not to say	38	11.2%
	More than €200,000	4	1.2%
	€100,000 - €199,999	16	4.7%
	€80,000 - €99,999	22	6.5%
	€60,000 - €79,999	36	10.6%
	€40,000 - €59,999	90	26.5%
	€25,000 - €39,999	74	21.8%
	€10,000 - €24,999	40	11.8%
	Less than €10,000	20	5.9%
	Other	2	0.6%
How would you describe your place of residence?	Urban	227	66.8%
	Suburban	80	23.5%
	Rural	33	9.7%
Do you have a driver's license?	Yes	310	91.2%
	No	30	8.8%
Do you own a car or do you have access to a car (either privately owned or car sharing)?	Yes	277	81.5%
	No	63	18.5%
What is your knowledge about self-driving vehicles?	No knowledge/never heard of it	2	0.6%
	I've heard about it but don't know exactly what it is	22	6.5%
	I have some understanding of it	109	32.1%
	I understand the concept quite well	75	22.1%
	I understand the concept well enough to explain it to others	132	38.8%
	Other	2	0.6%
Have you ever ridden in a self-driving vehicle?	Yes	82	24.1%
	No	144	42.4%
	Not completely self driving but in a vehicle with some automated features	114	33.5%
Q2_12_AVrel_Recod_Merged	Pedestrian / Cyclist	97	28.5%
	AV User	158	46.5%
	Decision Maker	23	6.8%
	Developer	62	18.2%
Valid		340	100.0%
Missing		0	
Total		340	

Model Fitting Information

Model	-2 Log Likelihood	Chi-Square	df	Sig.
Intercept Only	1053.458			
Final	980.677	72.781	37	<.001

Link function: Logit.

Goodness-of-Fit

	Chi-Square	df	Sig.
Pearson	1270.545	1255	.374
Deviance	968.775	1255	1.000

Link function: Logit.

Parameter Estimates

		Estimate	Std. Error	Wald	df	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
							Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Threshold	[Q3.6_2_AVinterestShared = 1.00]	-3.206	.830	14.924	1	<.001	-4.832	-1.579
	[Q3.6_2_AVinterestShared = 2.00]	-1.786	.816	4.793	1	.029	-3.386	-.187
	[Q3.6_2_AVinterestShared = 3.00]	-.561	.811	.478	1	.489	-2.150	1.029
	[Q3.6_2_AVinterestShared = 4.00]	.989	.817	1.465	1	.226	-.612	2.589
Location	[Q2.2_gender_REC=1]	1.098	1.185	859	1	.354	-1.225	3.421
	[Q2.2_gender_REC=2]	-.132	1.885	.005	1	.944	-3.826	3.561
	[Q2.2_gender_REC=3]	.200	1.887	.011	1	.916	-3.499	3.899
	[Q2.2_gender_REC=4]	-.014	.232	.004	1	.951	-.470	.441
	[Q2.2_gender_REC=5]	0 ^a	.	.	0	.	.	.
	[Q2.3_Age_REC=0]	-1.402	1.929	.528	1	.467	-5.183	2.379
	[Q2.3_Age_REC=2]	-1.906	1.614	1.395	1	.238	-5.069	1.257
	[Q2.3_Age_REC=3]	-.981	.609	2.595	1	.107	-2.175	.213
	[Q2.3_Age_REC=4]	-.336	.374	.811	1	.368	-1.069	.396
	[Q2.3_Age_REC=5]	-.282	.330	.733	1	.392	-.929	.364
	[Q2.3_Age_REC=6]	-.026	.269	.009	1	.924	-.553	.502
	[Q2.3_Age_REC=7]	0 ^a	.	.	0	.	.	.
	[Q2.4_educ_REC=1.00]	.009	1.463	.000	1	.995	-2.858	2.877
	[Q2.4_educ_REC=2.00]	.612	.670	.832	1	.362	-.702	1.926
	[Q2.4_educ_REC=3.00]	2.009	1.903	1.115	1	.291	-1.721	5.739
	[Q2.4_educ_REC=4.00]	-.312	.538	.335	1	.563	-1.367	.743
	[Q2.4_educ_REC=5.00]	.087	.350	.062	1	.804	-.599	.774
	[Q2.4_educ_REC=6.00]	.610	.298	4.201	1	.040	.027	1.194
	[Q2.4_educ_REC=7.00]	0 ^a	.	.	0	.	.	.
	[Q2.5_income_REC=1]	-.935	.544	2.953	1	.086	-2.001	.131
[Q2.5_income_REC=2]	.009	1.040	.000	1	.993	-2.030	2.047	
[Q2.5_income_REC=3]	.484	.668	.526	1	.468	-.825	1.794	
[Q2.5_income_REC=4]	-.218	.615	.125	1	.723	-1.423	.987	
[Q2.5_income_REC=5]	-.594	.541	1.205	1	.272	-1.654	.466	
[Q2.5_income_REC=6]	-.510	.481	1.126	1	.289	-1.452	.432	
[Q2.5_income_REC=7]	-.709	.488	2.111	1	.146	-1.666	.247	
[Q2.5_income_REC=8]	-.726	.522	1.935	1	.164	-1.749	.297	
[Q2.5_income_REC=9]	0 ^a	.	.	0	.	.	.	
[Q2.7_residence=1]	-.463	.352	1.734	1	.188	-1.152	.226	
[Q2.7_residence=2]	-.400	.389	1.055	1	.304	-1.163	.363	
[Q2.7_residence=3]	0 ^a	.	.	0	.	.	.	
[Q2.8_license=1]	-.403	.420	.917	1	.338	-1.227	.421	
[Q2.8_license=2]	0 ^a	.	.	0	.	.	.	
[Q2.9_carOwn=1]	.476	.313	2.314	1	.128	-.137	1.090	
[Q2.9_carOwn=2]	0 ^a	.	.	0	.	.	.	
[Q2.10_AVknowledge=1]	-21.364	.000	.	1	.	-21.364	-21.364	
[Q2.10_AVknowledge=2]	-.141	.496	.081	1	.776	-1.113	.830	
[Q2.10_AVknowledge=3]	.058	.288	.040	1	.841	-.507	.622	
[Q2.10_AVknowledge=4]	-.083	.302	.075	1	.784	-.675	.509	
[Q2.10_AVknowledge=5]	0 ^a	.	.	0	.	.	.	
[Q2.11_AVexperience=1]	.075	.288	.067	1	.795	-.490	.640	
[Q2.11_AVexperience=2]	-.255	.246	1.068	1	.301	-.737	.228	
[Q2.11_AVexperience=6]	0 ^a	.	.	0	.	.	.	
[Q2_12_AVrel_Recod_Merged=1.00]	-1.225	.354	11.951	1	<.001	-1.920	-.531	
[Q2_12_AVrel_Recod_Merged=2.00]	-.182	.325	.316	1	.574	-.819	.454	
[Q2_12_AVrel_Recod_Merged=3.00]	-.195	.483	.163	1	.686	-1.142	.752	
[Q2_12_AVrel_Recod_Merged=4.00]	0 ^a	.	.	0	.	.	.	

Link function: Logit.

a. This parameter is set to zero because it is redundant.

Test of Parallel Lines^a

Model	-2 Log Likelihood	Chi-Square	df	Sig.
Null Hypothesis	980.677			
General	866.849 ^b	113.828 ^c	111	.408

The null hypothesis states that the location parameters (slope coefficients) are the same across response categories.

a. Link function: Logit.

b. The log-likelihood value cannot be further increased after maximum number of step-halving.

c. The Chi-Square statistic is computed based on the log-likelihood value of the last iteration of the general model. Validity of the test is uncertain.

Case Processing Summary

	N	Marginal Percentage
How interested are you in using a self-driving vehicle in the following scenarios? - Owning my own. I would be responsible for finding a place to store it (similar to personal car ownership).		
Not at all interested	126	37.1%
Slightly interested	67	19.7%
Moderately interested	77	22.6%
Very interested	46	13.5%
Extremely interested	24	7.1%
How do you describe yourself? - Selected Choice		
Prefer not to say	3	0.9%
Prefer to self-describe	1	0.3%
Non-binary	2	0.6%
Female	136	40.0%
Male	198	58.2%
How old are you?		
Prefer not to say	1	0.3%
70+ years old	2	0.6%
61-70 years old	14	4.1%
51-60 years old	46	13.5%
41-50 years old	64	18.8%
31-40 years old	107	31.5%
18-30 years old	106	31.2%
What is the highest level of education you have completed?		
Prefer not to say	2	0.6%
Other	9	2.6%
Primary school	1	0.3%
Secondary / technical / vocational education	21	6.2%
Bachelor degree	73	21.5%
Masters degree	179	52.6%
PhD / post-graduate studies	55	16.2%
What is your personal annual income before taxes?		
Prefer not to say	38	11.2%
More than €200,000	4	1.2%
€100,000 - €199,999	16	4.7%
€80,000 - €99,999	22	6.5%
€60,000 - €79,999	36	10.6%
€40,000 - €59,999	90	26.5%
€25,000 - €39,999	74	21.8%
€10,000 - €24,999	40	11.8%
Less than €10,000	20	5.9%
How would you describe your place of residence?		
Urban	227	66.8%
Suburban	80	23.5%
Rural	33	9.7%
Do you have a driver's license?		
Yes	310	91.2%
No	30	8.8%
Do you own a car or do you have access to a car (either privately owned or car sharing)?		
Yes	277	81.5%
No	63	18.5%
Occupant of the self-driving vehicle, how important do you think it is to be informed about the following: - What types of information the vehicle's sensors recognise (e.g. weather conditions, people)		
NA	10	2.9%
Not at all imp	14	4.1%
Slightly imp	43	12.6%
Moderately imp	83	24.4%
Very imp	106	31.2%
Extremely imp	84	24.7%
Where self-driving vehicles operate regularly in traffic and you are an occupant of the self-driving vehicle, how important do you think it is to be informed about the following: - How the vehicle makes its decisions (e.g. to stop, give priority to others)		
NA	10	2.9%
Not at all imp	10	2.9%
Slightly imp	37	10.9%
Moderately imp	73	21.5%
Very imp	112	32.9%
Extremely imp	98	28.8%
Where self-driving vehicles operate regularly in traffic and you are an occupant of the self-driving vehicle, how important do you think it is to be informed about the following: - In what situations you, as the occupant, might need to take over control		
NA	11	3.2%
Not at all imp	3	0.9%
Slightly imp	4	1.2%
Moderately imp	15	4.4%
Very imp	70	20.6%
Extremely imp	237	69.7%
How important is it for you to be able to do work or recreational activities in a self-driving vehicle?		
Extremely important	21	6.2%
Very important	79	23.2%
Moderately important	93	27.4%
Slightly important	72	21.2%
Not at all important	75	22.1%
Valid	340	100.0%
Missing	0	
Total	340	

Parameter Estimates

Threshold	Estimate	Std. Error	Wald	df	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
[Q3_6_1_AVinterestOwn=1.00]	-1.107	.879	1.589	1	.207	-2.829	.614
[Q3_6_1_AVinterestOwn=2.00]	-.023	.877	.001	1	.979	-1.742	1.696
[Q3_6_1_AVinterestOwn=3.00]	1.337	.877	2.324	1	.127	-.382	3.057
[Q3_6_1_AVinterestOwn=4.00]	2.778	.891	9.714	1	.002	1.031	4.524
Location							
[Q2_2_gender_REC=1]	-.603	1.227	.242	1	.623	-3.008	1.802
[Q2_2_gender_REC=2]	23.241	8718.979	.000	1	.998	-17065.645	17112.126
[Q2_2_gender_REC=3]	-.967	1.369	.498	1	.480	-3.651	1.718
[Q2_2_gender_REC=4]	-.542	.236	5.288	1	.021	-1.004	-.080
[Q2_2_gender_REC=5]	0 ^a	.	.	0	.	.	.
[Q2_3_Age_REC=0]	-20.006	.000	.	1	.	-20.006	-20.006
[Q2_3_Age_REC=2]	-18.945	7775.289	.000	1	.998	-15258.231	15220.341
[Q2_3_Age_REC=3]	-.398	.647	.377	1	.539	-1.666	.871
[Q2_3_Age_REC=4]	-1.158	.418	7.675	1	.006	-1.977	-.339
[Q2_3_Age_REC=5]	.390	.343	1.295	1	.255	-.282	1.063
[Q2_3_Age_REC=6]	-.012	.289	.002	1	.966	-.579	.554
[Q2_3_Age_REC=7]	0 ^a	.	.	0	.	.	.
[Q2_4_educ_REC=1.00]	.427	1.466	.095	1	.771	-2.446	3.300
[Q2_4_educ_REC=2.00]	-.050	.708	.005	1	.944	-1.439	1.338
[Q2_4_educ_REC=3.00]	2.427	1.923	1.592	1	.207	-1.343	6.197
[Q2_4_educ_REC=4.00]	-.911	.612	2.217	1	.136	-2.110	.288
[Q2_4_educ_REC=5.00]	.012	.371	.001	1	.973	-.715	.740
[Q2_4_educ_REC=6.00]	.172	.317	.295	1	.587	-.450	.794
[Q2_4_educ_REC=7.00]	0 ^a	.	.	0	.	.	.
[Q2_5_income_REC=1]	-1.238	.582	4.530	1	.033	-2.378	-.098
[Q2_5_income_REC=2]	-1.377	1.076	1.638	1	.201	-3.485	.732
[Q2_5_income_REC=3]	-.105	.699	.022	1	.881	-1.476	1.266
[Q2_5_income_REC=4]	-.778	.664	1.370	1	.242	-2.080	.525
[Q2_5_income_REC=5]	-.206	.571	.130	1	.719	-1.325	.914
[Q2_5_income_REC=6]	-1.167	.511	5.212	1	.022	-2.169	-.167
[Q2_5_income_REC=7]	-.810	.513	2.487	1	.115	-1.816	-.195
[Q2_5_income_REC=8]	-1.055	.546	3.729	1	.053	-2.125	-.016
[Q2_5_income_REC=9]	0 ^a	.	.	0	.	.	.
[Q2_7_residence=1]	-1.027	.365	7.914	1	.005	-1.743	-.312
[Q2_7_residence=2]	-.582	.402	2.101	1	.147	-1.369	.205
[Q2_7_residence=3]	0 ^a	.	.	0	.	.	.
[Q2_8_license=1]	-.100	.469	.046	1	.830	-1.019	.819
[Q2_8_license=2]	0 ^a	.	.	0	.	.	.
[Q2_9_carOwn=1]	1.059	.354	8.935	1	.003	.365	1.754
[Q2_9_carOwn=2]	0 ^a	.	.	0	.	.	.
[Q4_3_1_occupantAVinfoSensors=0.00]	1.003	.673	2.224	1	.136	-.315	2.322
[Q4_3_1_occupantAVinfoSensors=1.00]	-1.952	.896	4.744	1	.029	-3.709	-.196
[Q4_3_1_occupantAVinfoSensors=2.00]	-.976	.494	3.893	1	.049	-1.946	-.006
[Q4_3_1_occupantAVinfoSensors=3.00]	-1.480	.404	13.403	1	<.001	-2.272	-.688
[Q4_3_1_occupantAVinfoSensors=4.00]	-.252	.351	.517	1	.472	-.939	.435
[Q4_3_1_occupantAVinfoSensors=5.00]	0 ^a	.	.	0	.	.	.
[Q4_3_2_occupantAVinfoDecisions=0.00]	0 ^a	.	.	0	.	.	.
[Q4_3_2_occupantAVinfoDecisions=1.00]	.112	.903	.015	1	.901	-1.658	1.883
[Q4_3_2_occupantAVinfoDecisions=2.00]	.010	.503	.000	1	.984	-.975	.995
[Q4_3_2_occupantAVinfoDecisions=3.00]	.200	.404	.246	1	.620	-.592	.993
[Q4_3_2_occupantAVinfoDecisions=4.00]	.506	.344	2.166	1	.141	-.168	1.180
[Q4_3_2_occupantAVinfoDecisions=5.00]	0 ^a	.	.	0	.	.	.
[Q4_3_3_occupantAVinfoTakeOver=0.00]	0 ^a	.	.	0	.	.	.
[Q4_3_3_occupantAVinfoTakeOver=1.00]	1.422	1.146	1.539	1	.215	-.825	3.668
[Q4_3_3_occupantAVinfoTakeOver=2.00]	1.624	.971	2.798	1	.094	-.279	3.526
[Q4_3_3_occupantAVinfoTakeOver=3.00]	1.052	.583	3.250	1	.071	-.092	2.195
[Q4_3_3_occupantAVinfoTakeOver=4.00]	.051	.288	.031	1	.860	-.514	.615
[Q4_3_3_occupantAVinfoTakeOver=5.00]	0 ^a	.	.	0	.	.	.
[Q4_6_impOtherActivREC=1]	1.366	.499	7.493	1	.006	.388	2.344
[Q4_6_impOtherActivREC=2]	1.784	.359	24.707	1	<.001	1.080	2.487
[Q4_6_impOtherActivREC=3]	1.085	.341	10.152	1	.001	.418	1.752
[Q4_6_impOtherActivREC=4]	1.242	.348	12.718	1	<.001	.560	1.925
[Q4_6_impOtherActivREC=5]	0 ^a	.	.	0	.	.	.

Link function: Logit

a. This parameter is set to zero because it is redundant.

Model Fitting Information					Goodness-of-Fit		
Model	-2 Log Likelihood	Chi-Square	df	Sig.	Chi-Square	df	Sig.
Intercept Only	1005.011				Pearson	1286.124	.625
Final	868.235	136.776	45	<.001	Deviance	865.462	1.000

Link function: Logit.

Test of Parallel Lines ^a				
Model	-2 Log Likelihood	Chi-Square	df	Sig.
Null Hypothesis	868.235			
General	706.770 ^b	161.465 ^c	135	.060

The null hypothesis states that the location parameters (slope coefficients) are the same across response categories.

- a. Link function: Logit.
- b. The log-likelihood value cannot be further increased after maximum number of step-halving.
- c. The Chi-Square statistic is computed based on the log-likelihood value of the last iteration of the general model. Validity of the test is uncertain.

Figure 36: OLR for the level of interest in owning an AV vs. different independent variables

Figure 37: Corresponding needs for a comfortable travel doing selected activities (if any) in a self-driving vehicle

Case Processing Summary

	N	Marginal Percentage
Travel in AV for: door-to-door commute	NA	50 14.7%
	Never	71 20.9%
	Yearly	25 7.4%
	Monthly	26 7.6%
	Weekly	53 15.6%
	Daily	115 33.8%
How do you describe yourself? - Selected Choice	Prefer not to say	3 0.9%
	Prefer to self-describe	1 0.3%
	Non-binary	2 0.6%
	Female	136 40.0%
	Male	198 58.2%
How old are you?	Prefer not to say	1 0.3%
	70+ years old	2 0.6%
	61-70 years old	14 4.1%
	51-60 years old	46 13.5%
	41-50 years old	64 18.8%
	31-40 years old	107 31.5%
	18-30 years old	106 31.2%
	Prefer not to say	2 0.6%
What is the highest level of education you have completed?	Other	9 2.6%
	Primary school	1 0.3%
	Secondary / technical / vocational education	21 6.2%
	Bachelor degree	73 21.5%
	Masters degree	179 52.6%
	PhD / post-graduate studies	55 16.2%
	Prefer not to say	38 11.2%
	More than €200,000	4 1.2%
	€100,000 - €199,999	16 4.7%
	€80,000 - €99,999	22 6.5%
€60,000 - €79,999	36 10.6%	
€40,000 - €59,999	90 26.5%	
€25,000 - €39,999	74 21.8%	
€10,000 - €24,999	40 11.8%	
Less than €10,000	20 5.9%	
How would you describe your place of residence?	Urban	227 66.8%
	Suburban	80 23.5%
	Rural	33 9.7%
Do you have a driver's license?	Yes	310 91.2%
	No	30 8.8%
Do you own a car or do you have access to a car (either privately owned or car sharing)?	Yes	277 81.5%
	No	63 18.5%
Occupant of the self-driving vehicle, how important do you think it is to be informed about the following: - What types of information the vehicle's sensors recognise (e.g. weather conditions, people)	NA	10 2.9%
	Not at all imp	14 4.1%
	Slightly imp	43 12.6%
	Moderately imp	83 24.4%
	Very imp	106 31.2%
	Extremely imp	84 24.7%
Where self-driving vehicles operate regularly in traffic and you are an occupant of the self-driving vehicle, how important do you think it is to be informed about the following: - How the vehicle makes its decisions (e.g. to stop, give priority to others)	NA	10 2.9%
	Not at all imp	10 2.9%
	Slightly imp	37 10.9%
	Moderately imp	73 21.5%
	Very imp	112 32.9%
	Extremely imp	98 28.8%
Where self-driving vehicles operate regularly in traffic and you are an occupant of the self-driving vehicle, how important do you think it is to be informed about the following: - In what situations you, as the occupant, might need to take over control	NA	11 3.2%
	Not at all imp	3 0.9%
	Slightly imp	4 1.2%
	Moderately imp	15 4.4%
	Very imp	70 20.6%
	Extremely imp	237 69.7%
How important is it for you to be able to do work or recreational activities in a self-driving vehicle?	Extremely important	21 6.2%
	Very important	79 23.2%
	Moderately important	93 27.4%
	Slightly important	72 21.2%
	Not at all important	75 22.1%
Valid	340	100.0%
Missing	0	
Total	340	

Parameter Estimates

Threshold	Estimate	Std. Error	Wald	df	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
[03_3_1_REC_AVtravelCommute=0.0]	-0.446	.844	.280	1	.597	-2.100	1.207
[03_3_1_REC_AVtravelCommute=2.00]	1.113	.844	1.740	1	.187	-.541	2.767
[03_3_1_REC_AVtravelCommute=3.00]	1.531	.846	3.277	1	.070	-.127	3.188
[03_3_1_REC_AVtravelCommute=4.00]	1.945	.848	5.263	1	.022	.283	3.606
[03_3_1_REC_AVtravelCommute=5.00]	2.774	.854	10.564	1	.001	1.101	4.447
[02_2_gender_REC=1]	1.302	1.298	1.007	1	.316	-1.241	3.845
[02_2_gender_REC=2]	20.838	.000	.	1	.	20.838	20.838
[02_2_gender_REC=3]	-2.407	1.510	2.543	1	.111	-5.366	.552
[02_2_gender_REC=4]	-5.398	.225	5.716	1	.017	-5.980	-.097
[02_2_gender_REC=5]	0 ^a	.	.	0	.	.	.
[02_3_Age_REC=0]	-19.933	9940.652	.000	1	.998	-19503.253	19463.387
[02_3_Age_REC=2]	-4.34	1.351	.103	1	.748	-3.083	2.214
[02_3_Age_REC=3]	-.291	.630	.213	1	.644	-1.526	.944
[02_3_Age_REC=4]	-1.537	.392	15.350	1	<.001	-2.305	-.768
[02_3_Age_REC=5]	-.810	.342	5.601	1	.018	-1.481	-.139
[02_3_Age_REC=6]	-.616	.287	4.618	1	.032	-1.178	-.054
[02_3_Age_REC=7]	0 ^a	.	.	0	.	.	.
[02_4_educ_REC=1.00]	-4.057	1.687	5.783	1	.016	-7.364	-.751
[02_4_educ_REC=2.00]	-.082	.741	.012	1	.912	-1.534	1.370
[02_4_educ_REC=3.00]	-1.885	1.907	.977	1	.323	-5.623	1.853
[02_4_educ_REC=4.00]	-1.807	.552	10.714	1	.001	-2.889	-.725
[02_4_educ_REC=5.00]	-.711	.364	3.812	1	.051	-1.425	.003
[02_4_educ_REC=6.00]	-.397	.311	1.632	1	.201	-1.006	.212
[02_4_educ_REC=7.00]	0 ^a	.	.	0	.	.	.
[02_5_income_REC=1]	1.278	.562	5.163	1	.023	.176	2.380
[02_5_income_REC=2]	.434	1.087	.159	1	.690	-1.697	2.566
[02_5_income_REC=3]	1.198	.712	2.833	1	.092	-.197	2.592
[02_5_income_REC=4]	.595	.652	.834	1	.361	-.682	1.872
[02_5_income_REC=5]	1.894	.579	10.695	1	.001	.759	3.029
[02_5_income_REC=6]	1.099	.501	4.812	1	.028	.117	2.081
[02_5_income_REC=7]	1.153	.507	5.165	1	.023	.159	2.148
[02_5_income_REC=8]	.855	.540	2.510	1	.113	-.203	1.912
[02_5_income_REC=9]	0 ^a	.	.	0	.	.	.
[02_7_residence=1]	.191	.366	.272	1	.602	-.526	.907
[02_7_residence=2]	.382	.405	.891	1	.345	-.411	1.175
[02_7_residence=3]	0 ^a	.	.	0	.	.	.
[02_8_license=1]	-.151	.430	.123	1	.726	-.994	.692
[02_8_license=2]	0 ^a	.	.	0	.	.	.
[02_9_carOwn=1]	1.454	.330	19.405	1	<.001	.807	2.102
[02_9_carOwn=2]	0 ^a	.	.	0	.	.	.
[04_3_1_occupantAVinfoSensors=0.0]	-1.835	.748	6.016	1	.014	-3.301	-.369
[04_3_1_occupantAVinfoSensors=1.00]	-.095	.718	.018	1	.894	-1.503	1.312
[04_3_1_occupantAVinfoSensors=2.00]	.794	.486	2.674	1	.102	-.158	1.746
[04_3_1_occupantAVinfoSensors=3.00]	-.300	.378	.631	1	.427	-1.042	.441
[04_3_1_occupantAVinfoSensors=4.00]	.631	.346	3.324	1	.068	-.047	1.310
[04_3_1_occupantAVinfoSensors=5.00]	0 ^a	.	.	0	.	.	.
[04_3_2_occupantAVinfoDecisions=0.0]	0 ^a	.	.	0	.	.	.
[04_3_2_occupantAVinfoDecisions=1.00]	-.057	.805	.005	1	.944	-1.634	1.521
[04_3_2_occupantAVinfoDecisions=2.00]	-.442	.480	.847	1	.357	-1.383	.499
[04_3_2_occupantAVinfoDecisions=3.00]	.252	.390	.416	1	.519	-.513	1.016
[04_3_2_occupantAVinfoDecisions=4.00]	-.053	.334	.026	1	.873	-.709	.602
[04_3_2_occupantAVinfoDecisions=5.00]	0 ^a	.	.	0	.	.	.
[04_3_3_occupantAVinfoTakeOver=0.0]	0 ^a	.	.	0	.	.	.
[04_3_3_occupantAVinfoTakeOver=1.00]	2.934	1.487	3.895	1	.048	.020	5.849
[04_3_3_occupantAVinfoTakeOver=2.00]	-2.469	1.052	5.511	1	.019	-4.530	-.408
[04_3_3_occupantAVinfoTakeOver=3.00]	.527	.552	.910	1	.340	-.556	1.609
[04_3_3_occupantAVinfoTakeOver=4.00]	-.504	.277	3.307	1	.069	-1.047	.039
[04_3_3_occupantAVinfoTakeOver=5.00]	0 ^a	.	.	0	.	.	.
[04_6_impOtherActivREC=1]	.697	.487	2.047	1	.152	-.258	1.653
[04_6_impOtherActivREC=2]	1.072	.332	10.391	1	.001	.420	1.723
[04_6_impOtherActivREC=3]	.936	.312	9.005	1	.003	.325	1.548
[04_6_impOtherActivREC=4]	.712	.321	4.911	1	.027	.082	1.341
[04_6_impOtherActivREC=5]	0 ^a	.	.	0	.	.	.

Link function: Logit

a. This parameter is set to zero because it is redundant.

Model Fitting Information					Goodness-of-Fit		
Model	-2 Log Likelihood	Chi-Square	df	Sig.	Chi-Square	df	Sig.
Intercept Only	1123.244				Pearson	1730.381	1640 .059
Final	988.247	134.997	45	<.001	Deviance	986.861	1640 1.000

Link function: Logit.

Test of Parallel Lines ^a				
Model	-2 Log Likelihood	Chi-Square	df	Sig.
Null Hypothesis	988.247			
General	707.743 ^b	280.504 ^c	180	<.001

The null hypothesis states that the location parameters (slope coefficients) are the same across response categories.

- a. Link function: Logit.
- b. The log-likelihood value cannot be further increased after maximum number of step-halving.
- c. The Chi-Square statistic is computed based on the log-likelihood value of the last iteration of the general model. Validity of the test is uncertain.

Figure 38: OLR for level of interest in using an AV for door-to-door commute vs. different independent variables

Figure 39: Expectations towards travel time and route control in an AV mobility system

Figure 40: Expectations towards traffic congestion, sustainability and fewer vehicles in an AV mobility system

Figure 41: Expectations towards ability to switch to manual driving in an AV mobility system

Figure 42: Concerns regarding AV behaviour and user's ability to operate an AV

Figure 43: Concerns regarding liability and level of comfort scenarios for self-driving vehicles

I would feel comfortable allowing my school-aged child to travel alone in a self-driving vehicle

I feel confident that I would be protected from cybersecurity breaches or data theft in a self-driving vehicle

I would feel comfortable about a self-driving vehicle making critical decisions where harm to humans is unavoidable

Figure 44: Concerns regarding travel of children, cybersecurity breaches, and decision-making in regard to AVs